

Intelligent Trust and Security Orchestration for 6G Distributed Cloud Environments

Deliverable 2.1

Use Case Requirements and Threat Surface Analysis

August 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15510043

Contractual Date of Delivery:	July 31, 2024
Actual Date of Delivery:	August 9, 2024
Editor(s):	Paulo Correia (PDM)
Author(s)/Contributor(s):	Luís Landeiro Ribeiro (PDM) Maxime Compastié, Saber Mhiri (I2CAT) Francesco Settanni, Cataldo Basile (POLITO) Diego R. Lopez, Jose Manuel Manjon, Lucia Cabanillas (TID) George Doukas (NTUA) Souvik Paul, Sheeba Backia Mary Baskaran (LNV) Stylios Klados (ADR) Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)
Work Package	WP2
Target Dissemination Level	Public

*This work is supported by the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139198, **iTrust6G** project. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or SNS-JU. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*

Revision History

Revision	Date	Editor / Commentator	Description of Edits
0.1	2024-03-05	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Template and ToC made ready
0.2	2024-04-03	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Reworked structure
0.3	2024-05-14	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Updated Introduction
0.4	2024-05-23	Maxime Compastié (i2CAT)	Updating Section 2 with General perspective on iTrust6G approach
0.5	2024-06-11	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Removed extra sub-sections of section 2
0.6	2024-06-17	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Review Structure and Taxonomies
0.7	2024-06-24	Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Scenarios and Use Case structured update
0.8	2024-07-10	Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Conclusions
0.9	2024-07-16	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Integration of partner contributions
0.91	2024-07-17	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Tables, figures and TOCs
0.92	2024-07-22	Souvik Paul (LNV) Sheeba Baskaran (LNV)	Internal Review Partner 1
0.93	2024-07-22	Stylianios Klados (ADR)	Internal Review Partner 2
0.94	2024-07-23	Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Merge Review Comment and apply corrections
0.95	2024-07-25	Maxime Compastié (i2CAT)	Quality Review
0.96	2024-07-26	Paulo Correia, Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Addressing Quality Review Comments
0.97	2024-07-28	Diego López (TID)	Updates to UC1 content and comments
0.98	2024-07-31	Luís Ribeiro (PDM)	Editing list of table and Index, update Bibliography to IEEE format
1.00	2024-08-08	Mir Ghorraishi (GIGASYS)	Final proof-reading and submission to EUC portal

Table of Contents

List of Acronyms	6
Executive Summary	8
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Scope of the document.....	9
1.2 Structure of the document	9
1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks.....	10
1.4 Expected audience.....	10
1.5 Methodology.....	11
1.5.1 Use case Analysis.....	11
2 Overview of iTrust6G concept.....	13
3 Use Cases for iTrust6G.....	18
3.1 Impact analysis.....	18
3.1.1 Enhanced human communication.....	18
3.1.2 Enhanced machine communication	18
3.1.3 Next generation services.....	19
3.1.4 Network evolution.....	19
3.1.5 Security and trust	19
3.2 Capabilities taxonomy.....	20
3.3 Stride threat modelling.....	21
3.4 Use cases.....	21
3.4.1 UC-01 Dynamic security orchestration and trust establishment in multi-stakeholder and multi-domain environment.....	21
3.4.2 UC-02 Operational security and trust re-evaluation	25
3.4.3 UC-03 programmable security as a service	29
4 Requirements	38
4.1 Requirement types	38
4.2 Common characteristics and scope	39
4.3 General requirements.....	39
4.4 Specific Requirements	41
5 Threat Modelling	44
5.1 Threat actors.....	44
5.2 Taxonomy	45
5.3 Attack vectors	46
5.4 Mitigations	46
6 Trust Key Performance Indicators	48
7 Traceability Matrix.....	52
8 Conclusions and Future Work	54

List of Tables

Table 3-1. Capabilities Taxonomy.....	20
Table 3-2. UC1-Scenario 1 Regular Description.....	23
Table 3-3. UC1-Scenario 1 Threat Modelling.....	24
Table 3-4. UC1-Scenario 2 Regular Description.....	24
Table 3-5. UC1-Scenario 2 Threat Modelling.....	25
Table 3-6. UC2-Scenario 1 Regular Description.....	27
Table 3-7. UC2-Scenario 1 Threat Modelling.....	28
Table 3-8. UC2-Scenario 2 Regular Description.....	28
Table 3-9. UC2-Scenario 2 Threat Modelling.....	29
Table 3-10. UC3-Scenario 1 Regular Description.....	32
Table 3-11. UC3-Scenario 1 Threat Modelling.....	33
Table 3-12. UC3-Scenario 2 Regular Description.....	33
Table 3-13. UC3-Scenario 2 Threat Modelling.....	34
Table 3-14. UC3-Scenario 3 Regular Description.....	35
Table 3-15. UC3-Scenario 3 Threat Modelling.....	35
Table 3-16. UC3-Scenario 4 Regular Description.....	36
Table 3-17. UC3-Scenario 4 Threat Modelling.....	37
Table 4-1. General Requirements.....	40
Table 4-2. Specific Requirements.....	41
Table 6-1. KPIs.....	48
Table 7-1. Use cases, Scenarios, and Requirements.....	53

List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
ABAC	Attributes-Based Access Control
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge
BCI	Brain-Computer Interface
CACAO	Collaborative Automated Course of Action Operations
CDM	Continuous Diagnostics and Mitigation
CMR	
CTI	Cyber-Threat Intelligence
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
CVSS	Common Vulnerability Scoring System
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service
E2E	End-to-End
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EPSS	Exploit Prediction Scoring System
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICS	Industrial Control Systems
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
ISG	Industry Specification Group
ISP	Internet Service Provider
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MR	Mixed Reality
MVNO	Mobile Virtual Network Operator
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NIS2	Network and Information Systems Directive 2
NoN	Network-of-Networks
PE	Police Engine
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
RA	Remote Attestation
RR	Remediation Recommender
SecMano	Security Management and Orchestration
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SO	Security Orchestrator
SSO	Single Sign On
SRS	Software Requirements Specifications
TA	Trust Algorithm
TM	Trust Management
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TTP	Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UX	User eXperience (UX)
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything

VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality
ZT	Zero Trust

Executive Summary

This document, iTrust6G D2.1, is an iTrust6G project work package 2 (WP2) deliverable. It focuses on two main aspects: documenting the use case requirements and conducting a threat surface analysis for the identified use cases.

In the first part of iTrust6G D2.1, the requirements gathered in task 2.1 (T2.1) are formally documented. This documentation involves eliciting requirements from various stakeholders, brainstorming sessions, and further analysis. The elicitation process actively engages stakeholders and promotes collaboration to uncover tacit knowledge, identify discrepancies, and reach a consensus on the project's requirements.

The elicited requirements are presented in a structured and standardized format, ensuring clarity, consistency, and completeness. The structured documentation follows a predefined template or outline, making it easier for stakeholders to understand and review the requirements. The requirements are organized into logical sections, such as functional requirements, non-functional requirements, security requirements, and performance requirements respectively.

The second part of the deliverable focuses on performing a threat surface analysis for the iTrust6G use cases. Threat surface analysis is a critical process that helps to identify, assess, and prioritize the potential entry points (attack vectors) that attackers could exploit to compromise the system's security.

Furthermore, the deliverable focuses on eliciting trust key performance indicators (KPIs) based on the threat analysis results. These KPIs will serve as measurable metrics to assess the trustworthiness and security of the iTrust6G system in the context of the identified threats and vulnerabilities.

Overall, iTrust6G D2.1 lays the foundation for the iTrust6G project by documenting the use case requirements in a formal and structured manner, conducting a thorough threat surface analysis, and defining trust KPIs. This deliverable is crucial for guiding the subsequent development and implementation tasks within the project, ensuring that security and trust are integral considerations throughout the process.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the document

iTrust6G D2.1 primarily focuses on eliciting and documenting use case requirements, conducting a thorough threat surface analysis, and defining trust key performance indicators (KPIs). It lays the foundation for the project by ensuring that the developed platform aligns with stakeholders' needs and is resilient against potential threats. The first key aspect of iTrust6G D2.1 is the comprehensive use case analysis and requirements elicitation. iTrust6G T2.1 (task 2.1) aims to develop a set of relevant use cases that capture the needs and requirements of various stakeholders and end-users. Elicited requirements are formally documented in a structured format. The use case analysis ensures that the iTrust6G platform is designed to address real-world challenges and align with the project's technical and functional vision.

Secondly a crucial component of iTrust6G D2.1 is the threat surface analysis. T2.1 performed a detailed examination of potential threats to the iTrust6G platform, identifying vulnerabilities and attack vectors that could compromise the system's security.

The threat surface analysis considers both internal and external threats, exploring how insiders or external attackers might exploit weaknesses. The findings from the threat surface analysis will be used to establish a comprehensive threat portfolio. This portfolio will serve as a valuable resource, guiding the development of the threat intelligence module and ensuring that the platform is built with robust security measures in place.

Based on the results of the threat surface analysis, iTrust6G D2.1 also focus on eliciting trust key performance indicators (KPIs). These KPIs will be measurable metrics designed to assess the trustworthiness and security of the iTrust6G system in the context of the identified threats and vulnerabilities. The trust KPIs will provide a quantitative means to evaluate the iTrust6G platform's resilience and its ability to maintain the trust of its users. By defining these KPIs, the project can establish clear benchmarks for success and track progress towards achieving a high level of security and trust.

It is important to note that while iTrust6G D2.1 contributes to the overall architecture of the iTrust6G platform, its primary focus is on the related use case requirements, threat analysis, and trust KPIs. The deliverable's findings will inform the architectural design process, ensuring that the platform incorporates the necessary security measures and aligns with the identified requirements. However, the detailed specification of the overall reference architecture will be addressed in a separate deliverable, i.e., iTrust6G D2.2 'Initial architecture of iTrust6G platform', and then iTrust6G D2.4 'Revised architecture and trust policy', will introduce the final design.

In summary, iTrust6G D2.1 plays a vital role in the project by conducting a comprehensive use case analysis, eliciting requirements, performing detailed threat surface analysis, and defining trust KPIs. This deliverable sets the stage for the development of a robust and secure platform that meets the needs of its stakeholders and end-users while effectively mitigating potential threats. The outcomes of iTrust6G D2.1 will guide subsequent tasks and deliverables, ensuring that the iTrust6G platform is built on a solid foundation of well-defined requirements, security considerations, and measurable trust indicators.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured in the following 8 chapters:

- Chapter 1 introduces the document with scope, structure, relation with WPs and tasks, expected audience and methodology.
- Chapter 2 presents an overview on iTrust6G concept, objectives and ambition and the relevance of the work program.

- Chapter 3 details the use cases for iTrust6G including the definition of taxonomy, scenarios and use case elicitation.
- Chapter 4 exposes the requirements.
- Chapter 5 presents the threat analysis with taxonomy, vulnerabilities and attack vectors along with possible mitigations.
- Chapter 6 provides the trust KPIs to be achieved.
- Chapter 7 details the traceability matrix relating the use cases with the application scenario and responsible partner.
- Chapter 8 concludes the document.

1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This section presents how this document is interconnected with other WPs and the related tasks of the project. iTrust6G D2.1 provides information regarding use case requirements and threat analysis to be used by the architecture design. The results of D2.1 extend to more than just the scope of WP2, as there is an influence on other WPs related to AI-driven threat intelligence, mechanisms on management of trust, orchestration features, integration efforts, and strategies of dissemination. The following points provide a detailed description of how D2.1 interfaces with each WP and some of the related tasks, emphasizing major contributions across multiple dimensions of the project.

- D2.1 provides basic inputs like use case requirements and threat analysis for further use and has a direct influence on project tasks in the form of guiding architectural decisions in WP2, T2.2.
- Its insights can be used to develop AI-driven threat intelligence systems to identify the threats and vulnerabilities for designing effective algorithms within WP3, T3.2 and T3.4.
- Although it's not stated explicitly, D2.1 indirectly allows identifying threats by enabling mechanisms for trust management in WP4.
- It is the insights from D2.1 that forms the design features, including AI-enabled security orchestration and programmability, which in turn influence the development of dynamic security processes and programmable mechanisms in WP5.
- Its outputs, such as use case requirements, are integrated in and validated against threats in integration and validation efforts within WP6.
- The insights from D2.1 are actively distributed to stakeholders and potentially exploited for innovation within the project, thus contributing to dissemination efforts and innovation management in WP7.

1.4 Expected audience

The expected audience for this deliverable would primarily include:

- The **iTrust6G project team members**, such as researchers, engineers, and project managers, will rely on the document to guide their work and ensure alignment with the defined requirements and objectives. They need to have a clear understanding of the use case requirements, potential threats, and trust key performance indicators (KPIs) to develop a secure and trustworthy 6G platform.
- The **European Commission and project reviewers**, who will assess the project's progress and adherence to the agreed-upon milestones. As the funding body, they will evaluate the quality and

completeness of the deliverable to ensure that the project is on track and meets its objectives.

- **Stakeholders and end-users** from various domains, such as telecom operators, service providers, and device manufacturers, who are interested in the iTrust6G platform and its potential applications. They will be keen to understand the use case requirements and how the project addresses their needs and expectations.
- **Standardization bodies and industry consortia** focused on 6G security and trust management, who may find the deliverable valuable for aligning their efforts and ensuring interoperability. They can use the information to contribute to the development of standards and best practices in the field.
- The **academic and research community** working on similar projects or in related fields, who may use the deliverable as a reference or learning resource.
- **Students and educators** in telecommunications, cybersecurity, and trust management can also benefit from the insights provided in the document.

While the deliverable is primarily intended for internal use within the iTrust6G project consortium and for reporting to the European Commission, it may also be shared with a wider audience to gather feedback, promote collaboration, and disseminate the project's findings.

1.5 Methodology

Use case analysis and requirements elicitation are critical components of the software development process, ensuring that the software meets the needs of its users and stakeholders. The IEEE standard guidelines provide a structured approach to capturing these requirements.

1.5.1 Use case Analysis

Use case modelling is a technique for capturing the functional requirements of a system. Use cases describe the interactions between a user (or "actor") and a system to achieve a goal. They are written as a sequence of simple steps, beginning with a user's goal and detailing the events that follow:

1.5.1.1 Guidelines for use case modelling

The IEEE does not provide a specific standard for use case modelling [1], but the practice is widely accepted and used in conjunction with IEEE standards for requirements analysis. The guidelines for use case modelling suggest that use cases should be written in a standard terminology as such we choose based on experience the following required properties:

- **Motivation and Business Rationale:** Describes the problem statement, market opportunity, and business drivers behind the use case. Explains why the use case is needed and valuable.
- **State of the Art/Starting Point:** Summarizes the current approaches and solutions in the market related to the use case. Provides context on where things stand today.
- **iTrust6G Novelty:** Highlights how the iTrust6G project uniquely addresses the use case in an innovative way beyond the state of the art. Clarifies the key differentiators.
- **Overall Use Case Description:** Provides a high-level end-to-end overview of the use case, including the main capabilities and how different components interact.
- **Stakeholder Involvement:** Lists the key stakeholders that play a role in the use case ecosystem, such as:
 - Network service providers

- Neutral hosts
 - Cloud providers
 - Application and content providers
 - Security solution providers
 - End users
- **Scenarios:** Presents a set of representative scenarios and examples that illustrate different flavours and instantiations of the use case.

Each use case scenario will be described using the following structure to capture the key aspects in a standardized way:

- Scenario name: A concise and descriptive title for the scenario.
- Rational and objective: Explains the purpose and goal of the scenario. Clarifies what the scenario aims to achieve and why it is important.
- Stakeholders' roles: Identifies the key stakeholders involved in the scenario and defines their respective roles and responsibilities.
- Preconditions: Specifies any assumptions, requirements or state that need to be in place before the scenario can occur.
- Procedure and workflow: Provides a step-by-step walkthrough of how the scenario unfolds. Describes the sequence of actions and interactions between different components and stakeholders.
- Dependencies: Lists any external systems, services, or resources that the scenario relies upon.
- Envisioned architectural functionality: Highlights the key functional elements from the iTrust6G architecture that enable and support the scenario.
- KPIs: Defines the main performance indicators and metrics to evaluate the success and effectiveness of the scenario.
- Benefits of iTrust6G approach: Explains the unique value and advantages that the iTrust6G platform brings for this scenario compared to alternatives.
- Entry points and trust levels: Identifies the main entry points into the iTrust6G platform for this scenario and specifies the required trust levels for each entry point.
- iTrust6G platform interface: Describes how the scenario interfaces and interacts with the iTrust6G platform.
- Operational service interface: Describes any interfaces to external operational services and systems that are needed for the scenario.
- Protected assets: Lists the key assets (data, infrastructure, services, etc.) that need to be protected in the scope of this scenario.
- Main flow: Provides an end-to-end walkthrough of the scenario, focusing on the main success path.
- Threat modelling: Analyses the potential threats, vulnerabilities and adversary motivations relevant for this scenario. Performs a risk assessment.

2 Overview of iTrust6G concept

The sixth generation of telecom networks (6G) will contribute to the conception and interconnection of future digital services thinning the border between physical worlds and benefits the needs of several verticals based on ambient connectivity such as vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication, eHealth, energy distribution and Industry 5.0. These new applications exploit the machine-to-machine communication, integrating a new set of multi-vendor and heterogeneous equipment at the heart of telecom infrastructure, fuelling the convergence between networks and IT systems. Consequently, this reinforces the criticality of network infrastructures as the compromise of a telecommunication network may not only generate service disruption and involve a loss of control on the data being exchanged, but it may also manifest impact in the physical world, representing new risks for our society.

In this context, 6G infrastructures are also characterised by the involvement of new stakeholders impacting the architecture of these networks and complicating the establishment of trust domains. First, 6G networks will feature a disaggregated architecture on the cloud continuum, involving the base stations at the extreme edge, edge cloud (mobile edge computing) and regional cloud, but will also leverage non-terrestrial resources such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) and satellites to support connectivity. Thus, new infrastructure providers will be involved in the operation of 6G networks, supporting their own technical context and security management and threat detection. Secondly, the development and operation of network appliances are benefiting from the cloudification, i.e. the adoption of service-based architecture, cloud-native technologies and cloud-optimised network procedures. This permits the elaboration of network functions using software fabrics from commercial off the shelves and open sources communities. This system relies on a wide range of third-party software components, which makes the software supply chain more complex and increases the challenge of managing potential vulnerabilities. Last, the 6G networks will allow operators to service their platforms to external verticals such as, mobile virtual network operators (MVNOs), internet service providers (ISPs) or enterprise networks. These actors act as tenants of the platform providers and carry their own security policies that may fall short in regards of the perpetually evolving threat landscape or miss the needed manpower or tooling to face cyber incidents, fostering the opportunities of lateral movements and diluting the network perimeter.

While the uncertainty on infrastructures, the security management in verticals and the design of the network services complicates the establishment of trust perimeters and traditional security architecture, the dynamic deployment of 6G applications driven by the service constraints make it inadequate and pleads for their continuous re-evaluation all along their lifecycle. This aligns with the architectural concept of "Zero-Trust" proposing that no participant in a network should be trusted and is leveraging the systematic evaluation of an entity to mediate its access to a restricted resource. In the context of 6G platforms, the security posture of operated 6G services can be constantly monitored to infer decisions on the access to platform resources (e.g. interface and infrastructure nodes). AI and ML algorithms have been successfully designed to detect malicious behaviours from entities and identifies based on lively extracted metrics and could contribute to evaluating their security posture to implement the zero-trust principles. Therefore, zero-trust architectures are foreseen as a powerful lever to maintain the resilience of the telecom infrastructure.

The protection of telecom infrastructure is an objective for telecom operator that is politically motivated by several directives from the European commission. For instance, the general data protection regulation (GDPR) protects the personal data consumed by service platforms by restricting the location where the personal data are to be processed and impose the disclosure of security incident involving personal data to data protection agencies. The NIS2 directive also defines an extensive cybersecurity regulation for the operator of essential services, including telecom operators, by imposing security requirements and reporting obligations, the practices for vulnerability management and demanding security assurance over the supply chains. From a technical standpoint, these regulations are holding the operators accountable for the security

compliance of a network platform and operated services, both from the perspective of design and the operation.

To enact this vision of zero-trust architecture for 6G platform, we need to scrutinise in depth the services in operation, from both a design (risk and conformity assessment) and operation (threat detection) perspective. In practice, this requires (i) extending the set of collected metrics to match the requirements from the AI/ML algorithms needed for threat detection and risk assessment, and (ii) extend the monitored surface area to obtain the needed visibility over the different component of the platform involved in the platform execution. The programmable environments will go hand-in-hand with 6G networks and represent a fertile ground to deploy and operate additional security enablers and can contribute to extending the monitoring capacity contributing to security posture evaluation if an adequate security management layer can be elaborated to serve the continuous trust evaluation of the network services.

Vision: iTrust6G will re-establish trust in 6G networks by delivering a platform exploiting zero-trust principles in 6G architecture, increasing the observability of network services, and enact a consistent, pervasive and explainable security management respecting the quality of service.

In iTrust6G, we propose a software defined ZT based security architecture, for 6G networks, centred around the four pillars of the proposal, namely,

- Zero-trust and incorporation of AI/ML for anomaly/threat detection & prediction
- Compliance-monitoring, and continuous threat assessment, for asset protection (Applications, Web, Data Bases (DBs))
- Intent-based security policy for explainable, AI/ML-enabled end-to-end security orchestration
- Enhanced observability via programmable interfaces & secure multi-tenancy support

The technical objectives of iTrust6G, listed in the project documentation are the following:

- 1. Design an End-to-End system security architecture that capitalizes on zero-trust principles to enable a trustworthy 6G service management platform, addressing dynamic network and application-level security requirements.**

This first objective entangles the integration of zero-trust principles in an anticipated 6G architecture. After identifying the assets and resources susceptible to benefits from zero-trust paradigm and the involved stakeholders, the project will define the main lifecycle for trust evaluation and security management, define a trust model among the stakeholders, and finally, define collaboration process between several stakeholders based on cyber-threat intelligence exchange.

The expected results of this objective are listed as follows:

- The general system architecture for trust and security in a multi-tenant 6G telecom platform, covering the cloud continuum,
- The definition of the main processes for the continuous trust assessment between services, computing resources, and users,
- The definition of the main processes for risk and threat evaluation on platform resources and mitigation,
- The definition of the main processes for the cyber-threat intelligence generation and ingestion for

trust assessment.

This objective will be met when the delivered system architecture fully supports the services and infrastructure resource requirements of proposed use cases in this deliverable (KPI-O1.1), when a trust model accounting for the architecture's properties, stakeholders and their trust relationship will be exploited by the use case for continuous trust evaluation (KPI-O1.2) and when the architecture covers the detection and the mitigation of the risks and threats determined by three use case families, covering distinct types of resources deployed on the cloud continuum (KPI-O1.3).

2. Exploit AI to detect novel threats from operated assets and generate pertinent cyber threat intelligence enacting their proactive protection.

Another objective contributing to iTrust6G concept is the involvement of the cyber-threat intelligence (CTI) to leverage inter-stakeholder collaboration. Specifically, cyber-threat intelligence describes indicators confirming the occurrence of cyber-threat (e.g. indicator of compromise) and how to mitigate it. In the context of iTrust6G, the CTI shall be used to better evaluate the reliability/trustworthiness of operated assets in interaction with a stakeholder, contributing to improving the trust assessment. It shall also be used to exchange remediation strategies among stakeholders to increase the general security stance of the platform, to be enforced proactively and reactively.

In essence, the expected results of this objective are:

- Definition of the monitoring requirements for security orchestration (for threat detection),
- A cyber-threat intelligence generation framework exploiting the monitoring interface and qualified threat to generate cyber-threat intelligence exchangeable amongst tenants,
- A meta-model serving the specification remediation playbooks sharable amongst tenant and exploiting the security programmability interfaces, and a framework to exploit them,
- A distributed vulnerability assessment framework inspecting the security posture of the services operated on the cloud continuum,
- An assurance conformity framework evaluating the posture of operated assets with respect to security regulatory referential.

The fulfilment of this objective will be quantified through the security monitoring of operated assets for the different use cases (KPI-O2-1), its application with CTI for threat detection , qualification and reporting (KPI-O2-2), the successful sharing of the CTI among different stakeholders (KPI-O2-3), the performance of vulnerability assessment (KPI-O2-4) and the application of the several security referential by the assurance conformity framework (KPI-O2-5).

3. Conceive novel Trust Algorithms (TA) exploiting AI integrated into trust management system (TM) accounting for forensics evidence.

To implement the zero-trust approach, iTrust6G envisions controlling the interaction of services operated over 6G architecture based on constant re-evaluation of their trustworthiness. To that end, iTrust6G contemplates the conception, development and implementation of a trust assessment algorithm and management system accounting for network service design, the stakeholders identity and the properties of the execution environment. The enforcement of trust decision will be finely controlled by an extended attributes-based access control (ABAC).

This work will generate the following results:

- A remote attestation framework continuously evaluating integrity posture of computing resources and operated asset contributing to trust evaluation,
- A distributed identity management encompassing network slices and infrastructure resources ownership, the ownership of operated assets, the involved actors in their supply chain and gauging their trust through an adequate model,
- An extended ABAC model accounting for trust properties and an access control monitor constraining the service orchestration,
- Authentication procedures and mechanisms for slices and network assets.

The outcome of this project will be measured through the applicability of the trust model to the three use cases (KPI-O3.1), the inference of trust from dependencies repositories (KPI-O3.2) and the detection delay from the remote attestation engine (KPI-O3.3).

4. Design and implement intelligent solutions for AI-driven security orchestration, across extreme edge, edge and public clouds (across the continuum) exploiting programmability models for pervasive enforcement.

The security posture of operated service is one aspect contributing to their trustworthiness. To that extent, **iTrust6G** will exploit security orchestration to maintain 6G network services into a trustworthy state, monitor security postures to contribute to trust evaluation and enforce remediation action, both at threat reaction time (reactive) and risk mitigation time (proactive).

The work toward this objective will materialise through the following technical results:

- The definition of programmability security model serving the monitoring, protection and the trust assessment of operated assets and computing resources in the cloud continuum,
- A catalogue of security enablers ready to be deployed,
- A security orchestrator serving the real-time monitoring and the lifecycle management of operated resources and constraining the service orchestrator for secured service orchestration.
- A secure-by-design resource generator, permitting the creation of ready-to-deploy resources supporting programmability models.

The successful accomplishment of this aspect of **iTrust6G**'s concept will be measured through the capacities of the threat detection (class of monitored resource - KPI-O4.1, type of detect threat - KPI-O4.2), the remediation (the duration of the selection of the security enablers - KPI-O4-3) and the performance of the programmability model (performance overhead - KPI-O4-4, and reconfiguration - KPI-O4-5).

5. Specify, develop and integrate intent-based security policies/engine, for explainable and automated E2E security orchestration.

To harness the multifaceted trust evaluation, **iTrust6G** shall provide capacity to stakeholders to specify in a holistic manner how the trust should be evaluated on network service and how to enforce it. More specifically, it shall address the translation of intent primitives into actionable workflows and policies related to threat intelligence, trust evaluation from compliance and technical context, reaction to security non-conformity, and secured provision/configuration of **iTrust6G** managed resources and services.

The expected results of this work are listed as follows:

- A policy format definition allowing the trust context definition and expected reaction to security incident,
- An extension of the TOSCA policy format expressing resource composition for security programmability model and trust constraints on resource orchestration.
- A policy engine exploiting the aforementioned policy formats to configure, (i) cyber-threat intelligence consumption and generation, (ii) trust evaluation from technical context, (iii) security orchestration, (iv) the security of the service orchestration on 6G services.
- An interpreter to explain the enforcement of the policies.

The fit-for-purpose of the policy model capacity with the use case needs (KPI-O5.1) and the efficiency of the policy interpretation (KPI-O5.2) are the prime evaluators.

6. Develop solutions for dynamic, configurable and intelligent placement of network functions over network slices and applications, to secure service design and delivery.

iTrust6G not only considers applying security orchestration to secure and maintain a certain level of trust in the environment, but also contemplate contributing to the security of the orchestration processes. A specific emphasis will be made on the security of delivery and network slicing protocol. In addition, the supporting service orchestrator will supervise the placement of network function in a user-friendly, automated and secure manner, and will implement a multi-level orchestration strategy.

The expected technical results of this work are:

- Extension of a service orchestrator to implement secure delivery protocol;
- Extension of a service orchestrator implementing trust-aware placement of network functions;
- Network slice manager accounting for tenant isolation; and
- Interpretation of the intent-based trust policy into placement configuration.

These technical results will be evaluated on the ability to handle threat incident (mean time to threat detection - KPI-O6-1, the mean time to response - KPI-O6-2, mean time to contain the threat - KPI-O6-3, mean time to identify an alert as a false positive - KPI-O6-4 and mean time to recover after a successful cyber-attack, KPI-O6-5), vulnerabilities (percentage of high-risk vulnerabilities - KPI-O6-6, mean time to risk mitigation - KPI-O6-7, percentage of accepted risk - KPI-O6-8) and integration of devices in the orchestration perimeters (mean time to identify untrusted devices on the network - KPI-O6-9, mean time to integrate new device - KPI-O6-10).

3 Use Cases for iTrust6G

The project has identified key use cases which will serve as the primary drivers for the development and validation of its innovative security concepts and solutions.

In the following sections, we introduce the taxonomy used to classify these use cases and provide a detailed elicitation of each use case family. This taxonomy and use case analysis will guide the design, development, and validation of iTrust6G.

3.1 Impact analysis

The advent of 6G networks promises to unlock a wide array of groundbreaking capabilities that will fundamentally transform how we communicate, work, and live. This business case analysis will explore several key areas where 6G is poised to deliver unparalleled value and enable disruptive new applications. We will dive into the potential of 6G to revolutionize human and machine communication, usher in a new generation of immersive services, evolve network architectures, and bolster security and trust.

3.1.1 Enhanced human communication

Enhanced human communication is expected to be one of the key capabilities enabled by 6G networks, building upon and significantly expanding the communication capabilities of previous generations.

Examples of enhanced human communication can be:

- **Immersive Extended Reality (XR):** 6G aims to enable truly immersive XR experiences, including augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality (MR). This will require extremely high data rates (up to 1 Tbps), ultra-low latency (<1 ms), and high reliability to support seamless integration of virtual and physical worlds. Applications include immersive telepresence, holographic communications, and extended reality workspaces.
- **Holographic Communications:** 6G envisions enabling real-time holographic communications, allowing for 3D holographic presence of remote participants. This will require massive amounts of data transfer and processing, necessitating advances in compression techniques, edge computing, and high-capacity wireless links.
- **Multisensory Communications:** Beyond audio and visual information, 6G aims to incorporate other sensory inputs like touch, smell, and even taste into communications. This will enable more natural and immersive interactions but poses significant challenges in terms of sensory data capture, transmission, and reproduction.
- **Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs):** Direct brain-to-computer and brain-to-brain communication is envisioned as a potential capability of 6G networks. This could enable thought-based control of devices or direct sharing of thoughts and experiences between individuals. Significant ethical and technical challenges remain to be addressed in this area.

3.1.2 Enhanced machine communication

Enhanced machine communication is expected to be a key capability of 6G networks, building upon and significantly expanding machine-type communications in 5G.

Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) in 6G aims to support ultra-dense networks of machines and IoT devices, with connection densities up to 10 million devices per km².

3.1.3 Next generation services

6G networks will allow for some new services that we can't do with today's networks. Some key things to understand in this context are:

- **Super-fast speeds:** 6G will be faster than 5G, letting you download huge files or stream high-quality 8k video.
- **New realities:** 6G will enable truly immersive virtual and augmented reality experiences.
- **Health and science:** Ultra precise remote surgeries or advanced scientific simulations could be possible.

3.1.4 Network evolution

6G represents a significant evolution in network architecture, intelligence, security, and capabilities compared to 5G and earlier generations. The integration of AI throughout the network is a key enabler of many of these advancements.

6G networks compared to previous generations:

- **Integration of AI/ML capabilities:** 6G networks will have pervasive AI and machine learning capabilities integrated throughout the network architecture. This allows for more intelligent and automated network management, orchestration, and optimization.
- **Distributed cloud architecture:** 6G will utilize a distributed cloud architecture spanning from the edge to the core network. This enables more flexible placement of network functions and services across the cloud continuum.
- **Intent-based networking:** 6G aims to enable more intuitive network management through intent-based interfaces and AI-driven orchestration.
- **Self-organizing networks:** 6G networks will have enhanced self-configuration, self-optimization and self-healing capabilities compared to previous generations.

3.1.5 Security and trust

As 6G enables transformative applications and services, ensuring the security, privacy, and trustworthiness of these networks becomes a critical differentiator and competitive advantage. Businesses that prioritize 6G security will be well-positioned to capitalize on the immense opportunities while mitigating the risks posed by an expanded threat landscape.

Key security considerations include:

- **Zero-Trust Architecture (ZTA):** 6G will adopt a "trust nothing, verify everything" approach, continuously authenticating and authorizing access. By continuously verifying and granting access on a need-to-know basis, ZTA enables businesses to secure their 6G-powered services and protect sensitive data, thereby strengthening customer trust and loyalty. [2].
- **AI-Driven Security:** Integrating AI and machine learning capabilities throughout the 6G network empowers businesses to detect and respond to threats in real-time. AI-powered anomaly detection, predictive threat analytics, and automated mitigation mechanisms enable self-healing networks, reducing downtime and ensuring service continuity. [3].
- **Quantum-Resistant Security:** With the advent of quantum computing, businesses must future-proof their security infrastructure. Investing in quantum-resistant cryptographic algorithms and exploring technologies like Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) positions businesses to maintain the integrity and

confidentiality of their communications in the post-quantum era. By proactively addressing quantum threats, businesses can ensure long-term data protection and maintain a competitive edge. [3]

- **Privacy Preservation:** As 6G networks generate and process vast amounts of data, robust privacy protection becomes a key differentiator. Businesses that implement advanced privacy-preserving technologies, such as homomorphic encryption and secure multi-party computation, can unlock the value of data while safeguarding user privacy. This not only ensures regulatory compliance but also fosters user trust, driving adoption and engagement with 6G-powered services. [2]

3.2 Capabilities taxonomy

The Capabilities Taxonomy provides a structured approach to define the essential operational domains and their associated capabilities, serving as a roadmap for the design, implementation, and management of the project. Table 3-1 is inspired on 3GPP Release 18 Stage 2, and personal work experience, they are presented as encompassing critical aspects such as infrastructure operations, security, trust management, and the integration of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning. We believe it presents a holistic perspective of 6G.

Table 3-1. Capabilities Taxonomy

Code	Category	Examples
O-01	Infrastructure Operations	Radio Access Network (RAN) Operations [4]
		Core Network (CN) Operations [5]
		Transport Network Operations
		Cloud Infrastructure Operations
O-02	Network Service Operations	Network Function Orchestration
		Network Slicing and Segmentation
		Service Lifecycle Management
O-03	Security Operations	Continuous Diagnostics and Mitigation (CDM)
		Security Information and Event Management (SIEM)
		Threat Detection and Remediation
		Vulnerability Management
		Identity and Access Management
		Data Protection Management
O-04	Trust Operations	Continuous Trust Evaluation and Re-evaluation
		Cyber Threat Intelligence Generation and Sharing
		Compliance Monitoring and Auditing
		Automated Cybersecurity Certification
O-05	AI/ML Operations	AI/ML Model Training and Deployment
		AI-driven Orchestration
		Anomaly Detection
		Predictive Analytics
O-06	Policy and Intent Management	Intent-Based Security Policy Definition
		Policy Interpretation and Enforcement
		Explainable AI for Policy Decisions
O-07	Multi-Tenancy Operations	Tenant Isolation and Resource Segregation
		Customized Management Spaces
		Conflict Resolution in Shared Environments
O-08	Programmability Operations	Security Programmability Models

		Secure Service Design and Delivery
		Programmable Security Enforcement

3.3 Stride threat modelling

STRIDE is a popular threat modelling methodology developed by Microsoft for identifying and classifying security threats. The goal of STRIDE is to help identify potential threats early in the software development lifecycle so they can be addressed and mitigated. It provides a structured approach for analysing a system's architecture and data flows to surface vulnerabilities. The name STRIDE is an acronym that stands for the six main threat categories:

- **Spoofing:** An attacker pretends to be a different user or system to gain unauthorized access. Examples include using stolen credentials or faking an IP address.
- **Tampering:** Data is maliciously modified, either in transit or at rest. This could involve altering database records, intercepting and changing network traffic, etc.
- **Repudiation:** A user denies performing an action and the system lacks the ability to prove otherwise. For example, a user transfers money but later claims they didn't authorize the transaction.
- **Information Disclosure:** Sensitive data is exposed to unauthorized parties, such as through a data breach, insecure data storage, or sending data unencrypted.
- **Denial of Service:** An attacker overwhelms system resources so that it cannot respond to legitimate requests. This could crash servers or make a website unavailable.
- **Elevation of Privilege:** A user gains higher-level permissions than they are authorized for and can perform actions they shouldn't be allowed to do.

To conduct STRIDE threat modelling, security experts examine system components, data stores, data flows, and trust boundaries. They consider each element through the lens of the STRIDE threats, identifying potential weaknesses. The risks are then assessed and prioritized based on likelihood and impact.

STRIDE provides a foundation for pinpointing security issues so that appropriate countermeasures can be implemented. While it originated at Microsoft, STRIDE has seen broad adoption across the cybersecurity industry and is a core component of many threat modelling approaches. [6]

3.4 Use cases

Use cases play a crucial role in the development of next-generation networks, particularly in the context of 6G. They serve as a bridge between the envisioned capabilities of the technology and the practical applications that will drive its adoption. Use cases help to identify the requirements, challenges, and potential benefits of new network architectures and services. In the context of 6G, use cases are being developed to explore novel applications that go beyond the capabilities of 5G, such as holographic communications, extended reality (XR), and ultra-reliable low-latency communications for critical services. The analysis of use cases is a critical component of the software development process, ensuring that the system meets the needs of its users and stakeholders. For 6G networks, use case analysis involves identifying key scenarios that will leverage the enhanced capabilities of the network, such as higher data rates, lower latency, and improved reliability. These use cases help in eliciting requirements, which are then documented in a structured format.

3.4.1 UC-01 Dynamic security orchestration and trust establishment in multi-stakeholder

and multi-domain environment

Evaluated 6G capabilities: O-01 Infrastructure Operations; O-02 Network Service Operations; O-03 Security Operations; O-04 Trust Operations; O-06 Policy and Intent Management; O-07 Multi-Tenancy Operations.

3.4.1.1 Motivation and business rationale

Understanding 6G as a *network-of-networks* (NoN) implies the participation of multiple stakeholders and the application of different technologies for the provision of any relevant service, and it raises several issues linked with procedures needed for the attachment and separation of the network domains, and procedures related to the proper and optimized operations of the E2E network service. The two reference scenarios described in the proposal have been refined, considering the implications of the edge-cloud continuum and cloud-native network infrastructures.

Network service orchestration procedures must consider the integration of networking solutions of different operators, limiting information exchange across domain boundaries, and considering the diversity in the lifetimes of the collaboration patterns, from short lived ad-hoc arrangements, as in the case of V2X links, to semi-permanent ones, with the paradigmatic example of MNO interconnections. These scenarios require the establishment of trust links among the control planes of the integrated domains, as well as a consistent way of support confidentiality and integrity within and across their data planes. Dynamic security orchestration system operates across different layers of the 6G network, involving various stakeholders to ensure comprehensive security coverage.

3.4.1.2 State of the Art/Starting Point

3GPP has defined some mechanisms [7] for secure network integration based on generalising mobile roaming procedures, and security considerations regarding non-3GPP (essentially, WIFI) access, though the approach does not go beyond the 3GPP framework, therefore not considering full E2E scenarios. On its side, ETSI ISG NFV [8] has generally focused on the Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) model applied to private clouds, typically owned by a single network operator, while it is commencing to consider the case of multiple cloud infrastructure providers, public and private, and the combination of different usage patterns.

3.4.1.3 iTrust6G Novelty

iTrust6G will provide mechanisms for the dynamic establishment (and release, equally important) of trust links across administrative and technology domains. These mechanisms are rooted at a pervasive identity infrastructure that allows the identification of all entities in the network, combined with mechanisms for identity management through entity interactions and the application of zero-trust principles to dynamically assess the trust links to be applied. Whenever an end user accesses a digital service, iTrust6G will provide a dynamic assessment of the security postures of the interaction across multiple domains, ranging from the physical infrastructure (cell towers) to the network layers (telcos and MVNOs) and the service layer (service providers).

3.4.1.4 Overall use case description

This use case addresses two different scenarios, archetypal for multi-party network service environments, and connected with the current trends in network service provision, such as the use of cloud-native technologies end-to-end, and the dynamic adaptation of network services by on-demand deployment of specific network functions.

3.4.1.5 Stakeholder involvement

The stakeholder involvement is defined as follows:

- **Network service providers** offer network services to end users or other network service providers by deploying and managing network functions on the communication infrastructure.
- **Neutral hosts** provide base physical infrastructure for user access, such as towers, antennas and edge sites.
- **Cloud providers** host in their datacentres the compute, network and storage infrastructure required to run the network and service functions.
- **Application and content providers** offer end users a variety of services that employ the network, edge and cloud infrastructures.
- **Security solution providers** develop and implement security technologies and protocols to protect the network and its users from cyber threats.
- **End users** are individuals and organizations that use the network to access applications and contents for any goal: communication, entertainment, and business.

3.4.1.6 Scenarios

The associated scenarios to this use case are:

- UC1-Scenario 1: Edge-cloud continuum and the use of cloud-native mechanisms
- UC1-Scenario 2: Dynamic provision of VNF

Table 3-1 to Table 3-5 present the regular descriptions and threat modelling of these scenarios.

Table 3-2. UC1-Scenario 1 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Edge-cloud continuum and the use of cloud-native mechanisms.
Rational/Objective	Support mobility along the edge-cloud continuum using iTrust6G security framework to provide zero-touch security to service workloads.
Stakeholders' roles	<p>Network service providers provide trusted connectivity services, and the trust roots to enable workload and user identities.</p> <p>Neutral hosts provide the infrastructure for edge workloads.</p> <p>Cloud providers provide the infrastructure for cloud workloads.</p> <p>Application and content providers provide applications suitable to be dynamically relocated across the edge-cloud continuum.</p> <p>Security solution providers provide specific security functions, deployed along the services, and suitable to be dynamically relocated across the edge-cloud continuum.</p> <p>End users request services and establish their service requirements in terms of latency, locality, security level.</p>
Pre-conditions	<p>End user with a service contract with a network service provider and an application provider, and optionally with a security solution provider.</p> <p>Edge and cloud infrastructures are available for hosting the application(s) required by the end user(s).</p>
Procedure/workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. End user request for a specific service, composed of different network and application functions, including service policy and requirements (in the form of intent). 2. Deployment is performed, according to trust assessment on the infrastructure and images. 3. At a point in time, some of the functions are required to migrate between the edge and cloud infrastructures, in the direction necessary to satisfy user intent. 4. The iTrust6G platform reassesses the trustworthiness of the new deployment scenario and rebuilds the trusted data plane links. 5. Function migration happens in a seamless manner, without impacting service
Dependencies	SSO, IDP, Remote Attestation
Envisioned architectural	Identity infrastructure is used for evaluating the identities of users, providers and workloads, and mediate interactions in the control plane.

functionality	Attestation is applied for workloads and network topologies. Trusted data plane links are built, based on user and function identities.
KPIs	Time for service deployment, following the application of security intents. Time for service reconfiguration, following the application of security intents. Impact of reconfiguration in service performance. Trust establishment among two or more stakeholders. Security policy reinforcement across two or more network admin domains.
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	Infrastructure and functional trust assessment. Interaction full traceability. Transparent dynamic functional relocation keeping required trust levels.

Table 3-3. UC1-Scenario 1 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofing	Inter-domain control plane and data plane interfaces	Attacker impersonates legitimate entities to inject unauthorized control requests or illegitimate traffic	High
Tampering	Inter-domain control plane interfaces, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms	Attacker modifies monitoring or control data or security controls to disrupt the service	High
Repudiation	Inter-domain control interfaces. iTrust6G audit mechanisms	Denial of attack or miscreant activity	Medium
Information Disclosure	Inter-domain control plane and data plane interfaces, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms	Attacker gains access to sensitive information in the protected network or the iTrust6G platform	High
Denial of Service	Inter-domain control plane and data plane interfaces, iTrust6G platform	Attacker overwhelms resources to disrupt network service and/or iTrust6G security enforcement	High
Elevation of Privilege	Inter-domain control interfaces. iTrust6G platform	Attacker escalates privileges across domain boundaries	High

Table 3-4. UC1-Scenario 2 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Dynamic provision of VNF
Rational/Objective	Support dynamic service reconfiguration, keeping trust level according to policy
Stakeholders' roles	<p>Network service providers provide trusted connectivity services, and the trust roots to enable workload and user identities.</p> <p>Neutral hosts provide the infrastructure for edge workloads.</p> <p>Cloud providers provide the infrastructure for cloud workloads.</p> <p>Application and content providers provide applications adequate to the required service functionality.</p> <p>Security solution providers provide specific security functions, deployed along the services, adequate to the required service functionality.</p> <p>End users request services and establish their service requirements in terms of latency, locality, security level</p>
Pre-conditions	End user with a service contract with a network service provider and an application provider, and optionally with a security solution provider. A service already deployed for the user at the network, edge and cloud infrastructures, according to the user declared intent.
Procedure/workflow	1. A new VNF is required to be deployed to address a security threat. Typically, as part of an attack remediation procedure, but can also be due to a change in user intent or a

	<p>periodic update procedure.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The new VNF is attested, and the appropriate location for it (including its trustworthiness assessment) is identified. The new VNF is deployed, and connectivity at the control and data planes restructured according to user identity and declared intent. VNF is activated and becomes part of the service, without impacting it.
Dependencies	SSO, IDP, Remote Attestation
Envisioned architectural functionality	<p>Identity infrastructure is used for evaluating the identities of users, providers and workloads, and mediate interactions in the control plane.</p> <p>Attestation is applied for the new VNF and the updated topology.</p> <p>Trusted data plane links are redefined, based on user and VNF identities.</p>
KPIs	<p>Time for VNF deployment, following the application of security intents.</p> <p>Time for service reconfiguration, following the application of security intents.</p> <p>Trust establishment among two or more stakeholders.</p> <p>Security policy reinforcement across two or more service domains.</p>
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	<p>Infrastructure and functional trust assessment</p> <p>Interaction full traceability</p> <p>Transparent dynamic VNF deployment and activation, according to the applicable trust levels</p>

Table 3-5. UC1-Scenario 2 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofing	NFV orchestration stack, deployed VNF data plane interfaces	Attacker impersonates legitimate entities in the orchestration stack, or uses an illegitimate VNF interface	Medium
Tampering	NFV orchestration stack, deployed VNF control or data interfaces	Attacker modifies orchestration data for monitoring and/or control, or data processed through the deployed VNF	High
Repudiation	NFV orchestration stack, deployed VNF control interfaces	Attacker denies involvement in illegitimate actions.	Medium
Information Disclosure	iTrust6G platform security mechanisms, NFV orchestration stack, deployed VNF control or data interfaces	Attacker gains access to sensitive information through the deployment procedures or use of the new VNF	High
Denial of Service	NFV orchestration stack, network control or data planes	Attacker uses the new deployed VNF to disrupt the network service and/or the NFV orchestration procedures	High
Elevation of Privilege	NFV orchestration stack, network control plane	Attacker uses the new deployed VNF to escalate orchestration or control plane privileges	High

3.4.2 UC-02 Operational security and trust re-evaluation

Evaluated 6G capabilities: O-03 Security Operations; O-04 Trust Operations; O-05 AI/ML Operations; O-07 Multi-Tenancy Operations

3.4.2.1 Motivation and business rationale

As critical applications such as autonomous vehicles, remote healthcare, and industrial automation will increasingly rely on future 6G networks, it is important to ensure robust operational security to maintain the integrity and availability of these critical services. 6G networks integrated with IT systems will have complex architectures that will call for more advanced security mechanisms to protect against advanced cyber threats. This use case focuses on validating the operational security mechanisms of the iTrust6G platform to ensure that it can detect, mitigate, and perform forensic analysis on attacks, thereby maintaining trust and compliance with security policies.

3.4.2.2 State of the art

Current state-of-the-art security mechanisms in 5G and earlier networks include basic intrusion detection systems (IDS), firewalls, and security information and event management (SIEM) systems. These solutions, however, are likely to struggle in meeting the security demands of future 6G networks for several reasons:

- **Massive data processing challenges:** The extremely high data rates and traffic volumes in 6G networks will pose significant challenges for security solutions like IDS in terms of attack detection, AI/ML pipelines, traffic analysis and pervasive encryption. Centralised security systems will have difficulty handling the massive traffic processing requirements. [9]
- **Highly dynamic and complex network architecture:** 6G networks will be much more open, virtualized and distributed compared to 5G. The distinction between inside and outside the network will blur. Conventional perimeter-based security tools like firewalls will not be strong enough to protect against external attackers in this environment.
- **Diverse new use cases and requirements:** 6G will enable a wide variety of new applications like UAVs, smart grids, XR, etc. which will have very stringent and varying security requirements. Existing security solutions designed for 5G may not be well suited for these use cases. For example, the high mobility of devices will require frequent changes of edge networks and security configurations. [9]
- **New threat landscapes:** The introduction of novel 6G technologies like THz communications, VLC, blockchain, AI/ML, etc. will also give rise to new types of security vulnerabilities and attacks that current solutions are not equipped to handle. More intelligent and adaptive security approaches will be needed.

3.4.2.3 iTrust6G novelty

iTrust6G introduces an innovative zero-trust enabled platform with built-in AI for mitigating and determining security threats on-the-fly. The system offers continuous monitoring and real-time response features, strong trust re-establishment protocols, and strategic forensic capability for complete attack prediction. The iTrust6G platform architecture integrates a cyber-threat intelligence layer for the generation, consumption and sharing of threat knowledge among multiple tenants. This allows exchanging CTI to facilitate evaluating the security posture of assets and inferring trust.

WP3 will produce a cyber-threat intelligence generation framework that exploits monitoring and detection capabilities to elicit sharable knowledge about detected threats in one tenant, to enable proactive remediation in other tenants (Result R3.2). AI will correlate indicators to determine the precise security posture of affected assets.

The shared CTI will be complemented with remediation playbooks to assist tenants in proactively mitigating their risk exposure (Result R3.3).

WP4 works on research and develop a trust evaluation module captures the trust context of an entity by indicators such as the integrity of nodes/services, existence of relevant vulnerabilities, and current exploitation campaigns revealed by exchanged CTI (Result R4.3). This influences access control and security orchestration decisions.

Quantitative parameters and trust indicators are used to continuously re-evaluate each CTI source and derive an overall trust score. The quality and reliability of CTI sources is assessed by examining factors like the type of information, source reputation, timeliness and accuracy.

3.4.2.4 Overall use case description

The purpose of this use case is to validate the robustness of iTrust6G's operational security mechanisms

under attack conditions. It involves testing the platform's effectiveness in detecting and mitigating multiple concurrent attacks, re-establishing trust in compromised systems, and conducting root-cause analysis to predict future attacks.

3.4.2.5 Stakeholder involvement

Stakeholder involvement are as follows:

- **Telecom Operators:** Implement and manage the iTrust6G platform within their networks.
- **Critical infrastructure providers (e.g., smart grid operators):** Ensure the secure operation of critical infrastructure’s components.
- **Security Administrators:** Monitor and respond to security incidents using iTrust6G tools.
- **End-users:** Benefit from enhanced security and trust in 6G-enabled services.

3.4.2.6 Scenarios

The associated scenarios to this use case are:

- UC2-Scenario 1: Back-to-back distributed attacks on an operational service
- UC2-Scenario 2: Trust re-establishment in case of compromised trust chain

Table 3-6 to Table 3-9 present the regular descriptions and threat modelling of these scenarios.

Table 3-6. UC2-Scenario 1 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Back-to-back distributed attacks on an operational service
Rational/Objective	Test the robustness of iTrust6G’s detection and mitigation mechanisms against persistent attackers.
Stakeholders’ roles	Network service providers Manage network and security infrastructure. Security Administrators: Oversee detection and response processes.
Pre-conditions	Multiple domains with active services and potential vulnerabilities.
Procedure/workflow	<p>Initiate back-to-back attacks, observe detection and mitigation, analyse response times. Telecom operators and critical infrastructure providers deploy and manage their services across multiple domains. Consequently, security administrators set up the iTrust6G Zero-trust based platform to continuously verify trust across the network and monitor for deviations from the baseline.</p> <p>An adversary launches an attack targeting the network infrastructure, as iTrust6G’s security threat detection identifies the abnormal traffic patterns, sends alerts, and adjusts network configurations to isolate attack traffic and maintain service availability. iTrust6G utilizes cyber threat intelligence (CTI) collected from both external and internal sources to craft ad-hoc remediations for mitigating risks originating from threats. These remediations, leveraging CACAO playbooks [10], will be used to dynamically adjust defences. The adjustments may involve reconfiguring security controls (e.g., for implementing more granular access control) or implementing changes in the information systems at risk (e.g., adding new security controls for enhancing protection and mitigating risks, isolating misbehaving or compromised entities).</p> <p>All collected evidence of the attack and the enacted response is eventually used to produce enriched CTI to be shared across domains, enabling informed collaborative responses, uniform responses to similar threats, and providing insights on the general threat landscape to all the involved parties.</p> <p>The security orchestration within the iTrust6G platform coordinates a comprehensive response across all domains, through CTI exchange, to help speed up isolation of compromised nodes and deploying patches or configuration changes.</p> <p>A detailed forensic analysis is conducted using the iTrust6G platform to understand the attack vectors and methodologies, as trust evaluation is reconducted to ensure that all</p>

	systems and components meet security and trust requirements before being reintegrated.
Dependencies	Availability of a realistic testbed environment.
Envisioned architectural functionality	AI-based threat detection, real-time mitigation, security orchestration.
KPIs	Attack detection and mitigation with two or more concurrent attacks. Variant/mutated threat prediction based on the forensics analysis of the previous attack
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	Enhanced detection and rapid response capabilities.

Table 3-7. UC2-Scenario 1 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofting	6G network interface, operational service interface	Attacker impersonates legitimate entities to gain unauthorized access	High
Tampering	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms	Attacker modifies data or security controls to disrupt the service	High
Repudiation	6G network interface, operational service interface	Attacker denies involvement in the attacks	Medium
Information Disclosure	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms	Attacker gains access to sensitive information	High
Denial of Service	6G network, operational service, iTrust6G platform	Attacker overwhelms resources to disrupt the service	High
Elevation of Privilege	Operational service interface, iTrust6G platform	Attacker escalates privileges to perform more damaging actions	High

Table 3-8. UC2-Scenario 2 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Trust re-establishment in case of compromised trust chain
Rational/Objective	Demonstrate the strength of trust algorithms when entities in the trust chain are compromised
Stakeholders' roles	Telecom Operators: Implement trust protocols. Security Administrators: Monitor and verify trust re-establishment.
Pre-conditions	Deployed 6G network, Compromised trust chain entities.
Procedure/workflow	Identify compromised entities, re-establish trust, verify continuity of services. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous security monitoring systems to detect anomalies indicating compromised entities in the trust chain. The remote attestation (RA) engine identifies the tampered node resource and network service. The system triggers alerts upon detecting these anomalies, and the Police Engine (PE) analyses these alerts against policy database entries and threat intelligence inputs from cyber-threat intelligence (CTI) and active malevolent activities. The compromised entities are isolated by the Policy Enforcement Points (PEPs) as instructed by the Policy Administrator (PA) to prevent further propagation of malicious activities. Security administrators assess the scope and impact of the compromise. The iTrust6G platform initiates trust re-establishment protocols. The PE uses the TA to evaluate the integrity of the compromised entities and the overall trust chain, considering user roles, attributes, and threat intelligence. The remote attestation framework evaluates the integrity posture of the nodes and service instances in operation. An AI model continuously monitors the execution of services to assess the current trust posture. The PA configures the corresponding PEPs to implement the required security measures, such as replacing compromised keys, certificates, and other trust anchors.

Dependencies	<p>7. New trust credentials are generated and deployed across the components. The Security Function (SF) containing firewalls and other security measures is updated to block any malicious data from reaching critical nodes.</p> <p>8. Security administrators verify the re-established trust chain using the trust management system (TM), ensuring all components meet the required trust standards.</p> <p>9. Continuous monitoring is reinstated to validate the integrity and functionality of the updated trust chain, supported by AI-based scrutiny of operated resources.</p> <p>10. Previously blocked services are restored, ensuring seamless continuity in critical services (e.g., electricity distribution in smart grids)</p> <p>Lessons learned from the incident are used to update security policies and procedures. AI-based detection systems are retrained to predict and mitigate similar attacks in the future.</p>
Envisioned architectural functionality	Secure communication channels, trust evaluation tools.
KPIs	Trust re-establishment time, service continuity, compliance with security policies.
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	Robust trust management and quick recovery from trust breaches.

Table 3-9. UC2-Scenario 2 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofing	Operational service entities	Attacker impersonates a legitimate entity to gain trust	High
Tampering	Operational service trust relationships, iTrust6G trust evaluation mechanisms	Attacker modifies trust relationships or trust evaluation processes	High
Repudiation	Operational service entities, iTrust6G platform	Attacker denies involvement in the trust compromise	Medium
Information Disclosure	Operational service trust relationships, iTrust6G trust evaluation data	Attacker gains access to sensitive trust information	High
Denial of Service	iTrust6G trust re-establishment processes	Attacker disrupts the trust re-evaluation and re-establishment	High
Elevation of Privilege	Operational service entities, iTrust6G platform	Attacker escalates privileges to manipulate trust relationships	High

3.4.3 UC-03 programmable security as a service

3.4.3.1 Motivation and business rationale

The 6th generation of mobile networks is expected to be more open than this predecessor to cope with new connectivity needs and use case. This openness stems into new requirements on networks infrastructure that involves additional actors:

- The increased integration of networks to capitalise on legacy networks and specific infrastructure (e.g. non-terrestrial resources) induces an increased numbers of infrastructure provider providing specific and heterogeneous computing resources and data plane resource to secure,
- The network exposure interface to create new services exposing network feature, network control and data analytic with third party applications involved new service providers and entities interacting

with the capabilities of the network,

- The continuous upgradation of the network software fabric is anticipated to capitalise on the desegregation of network appliances into cloud-native and micro-serviced applications provided from multiple software providers. These applications are anticipated to come from service providers' proprietary code, commercial off-the-shelve (COTS) from solutions vendors and open-source software (OSS) made publicly available.

Therefore, this openness is anticipated to limit capital expenditures (CapEX) and operational (OpEx) for the next generation of network while maximising their utility.

However, these requirements induce several security challenges that may jeopardise (i) service-level agreement, (ii) judiciary liability and (iii) respect of legal obligation toward critical service providers (e.g. Important entities and Essential entities in NIS2 terminology):

- The limited observability over infrastructure, platform and network service limits the availability of data to evaluate the security posture of a domain to detect vulnerabilities and threats. This directly impacts the capacity of evaluating a deployment environment as trustable, but also the confidence of the decision process in security management. Considering the anticipated composite nature of the 6G network, this also questions the capacity to generate rich threat intelligence to foster inter-providers security collaboration.
- Moreover, the current security enforcement methods in software networks rely on (i) network topology reconfiguration, (ii) security enablers lifecycle operation and configuration. One question arises as per the capacity of security enablers to interface and collaborate with services needing protect to enforce the security policy desiderata while maintaining the security overhead minimal to prevent service outage and service-level agreement compliance.
- Finally, numerous applications and resource cases require specific implants, to be developed, made available off-the-shelves, to be accessed as a service. Finding the adequate security mechanism to deploy and ensure its technical alignment and configuration will become more tedious as different provider integrates their services in the network layer and exploit application acting as third party to benefit from 6G capabilities.

In this use case, we propose to explore the applicability of security programmability to (i) increase the observability of network resources, (ii) decouple the security management from the technical context of resources facilitate security orchestration, and (iii) compose adequate security enablers to ensure scalability, minimum security overhead, and facilitate security self-configuration.

3.4.3.2 State of the Art/Starting Point

Security programmability is considered as an important enabler for automation of next generation management & intelligent orchestration (M&O) systems. The softwarization of networks has resulted in considerable savings in terms of the capital and operational expenditures of operators by mitigating the vendor lock-in of the network appliances and applying management methodologies, proven in cloud environments: network services (VNFs), possibly built from open source software are deployed, configured, scaled and deallocated as virtualized resources on the top of computing infrastructure (NFV Infrastructure, NFVI), either provided by the operator themselves or provided by an on-demand computing services. However, full exploitation and leveraging of the capacity of new softwarized environments, requires the automation of the management activities since the complexity of management interfaces, the scattered distribution of the resources on the cloud-to-edge continuum and interest in dynamic service provision, has out-stripped the capacity of the human operators. This effort is further complicated by the technical heterogeneity of the resources to be deployed and configured. Therefore, there is a need for a standardised

set of interfaces and procedures to be homogeneously deployed and operated. In the meantime, the exposure of the networks to larger attacker surfaces stresses the need to ensure services remain in an innocuous state and plead for conducting automated threat detection and mitigation actions. Software-defined networks have partially contributed to securing the network layers: By capitalising on the programmability interfaces, previous approaches have extended the management layer to cover threat mitigation processes: For instance, SDSecurity [11] presents an experimental framework for configuring and benchmarking security rules applied to network flows. Approaches such as FRESCO support modular security functions that can be then composed into security chains to protect resources but are often limited to specific enforcers. Security Management and Orchestration (SecMANO [12]) exploits orchestration languages to support access control policies, specifically in relation to VNFs. Other approaches have proposed extending data plane resources to natively conduct security enforcement actions. For instance, ETSI has issued the network management and monitoring specification for NFV resources while IETF has specified specific interfaces for network security functions relying on the SDN framework. In practice, H2020 PALANTIR [13] extends regular ETSI-compliant NFV orchestrator and VNF services interfaces to conduct security orchestration threat detection and mitigation enforcement. The main limitation of these approaches resides in their limited enforcement capacity limited to the network layer. Given the vulnerable nature of system architectures, alternative approaches have been investigated to inject and control security enablers at an intrinsic level of service instance. An extended TOSCA policy specifies the integration and operation processes. Nonetheless, the programmability models are limited to the generation of unikernel VM resources and don't confer to the enabler any trustworthiness guarantees during resource exploitation.

3.4.3.3 iTrust6G novelty

Security programmability will increase the capacity of a party involved in the operation of network service to obtain additional security features that are (i) fitting the requirement of a trust and security policies and are (ii) technically bound to the resources to protect and (iii) dwarf the induced overhead on performance. More specifically, security programmability will contemplate the access to additional monitoring metrics and enforcement capabilities available normally in situ of the resource to protect by injecting adequate security logic in the resource to protect and evaluate.

- In first case, the access to additional data will allow increasing the pertinence of the security and trust situation, allowing a more confident decision-making process trust evaluation and threat to handle;
- In the second case, the access to internal features of a resource will enable more precise mitigation actions with a limited overhead, and with local decision-making.

3.4.3.4 Overall Use Case Description

This use case addresses consider different scenarios to showcase contribution security programmability to the trustworthiness of iTrust6G processes, at different level of the architecture. The evaluation is to be conducted both in single-party and multi-party networks service environments.

3.4.3.5 Stakeholder involvement

In this use case, we foresee the following class of actors in interaction to showcase the benefits of security programmability:

- **Developers of the programmable security services (Application Developers):** This actor provides in a catalogues programmable security enablers that confidently adapt to technical context and a subset of resource and confidently satisfy security requirements stated from a security policy.
- **Network service providers:** These actors incorporate different services to deliver and operate a

network service fulfilling the business objective of an end-user. This actor is accountable for the resource in operation, the satisfaction of SLA, and is liable from the perspective of resilience regulation.

- **Infrastructure providers:** different actors in charge of providing computing resource and data plane resource in a cloud edge continuum, exploited by network service providers. They are contractually bound to the network service provider to deliver their service, while sharing their resources with other (and possibly competing) network service providers. Their trust need assessed continuously (zero-trust)
- **Attackers:** These actors are motivated by the compromise of network service operation to obtain a benefit. They conduct attacks to compromise deployed services, possibly leveraging weakness from the operated software asset (from the network service providers) and the infrastructure providers. Their activity is against specified security policies can however be revealable via carefully selected enablers.

3.4.3.6 Scenarios

The associated scenarios to this use case are:

- UC3-Scenario 1: Threat detection and mitigation
- UC3-Scenario 2: Dynamic trust evaluation
- UC3-Scenario 3: Generation of threat intelligence
- UC3-Scenario 4: Proactive risk mitigation

Table 3-10 to Table 3-17 present the regular descriptions and threat modelling of these scenarios.

Table 3-10. UC3-Scenario 1 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Threat detection and mitigation
Rational/Objective	These scenarios evaluate how the iTrust6G platform reacts to malicious activities from malevolent actors and leverage security programmability.
Stakeholders' roles	The Developer of the programmable security services provides in a catalogue the security enablers to be deployed that are serving threat detection and mitigation. The attacker conducts malicious activities with the objective to subvert a network service. The network service providers operate a network service for business purpose on a certain infrastructure, but the appliance s/he deployed contains exploitable software flaws. The infrastructure provider proposes and host network services and security enablers of multiple network service operators.
Pre-conditions	The security enablers are made available in the catalogue. A vulnerable network service is instantiated by a network service provider, on an infrastructure. Monitoring enablers are already deployed. The attacker has initiated an attack campaign.
Procedure/workflow	1. The monitoring enablers exposed security metrics from the internal of a network service. 2. The SIEM collect them, determine a threat occurrence, and issue an alarm to the AI-driven security decision module. 3. The AI-driven module collects additional contextual data and determine which action to undertake by selecting the adequate remediation (CACAO) playbook. 4. The remediation recommender execute assesses if all the needed security enablers needed to enforcement are deployed. 5. If not, the RR contacts the CMR to request the selection of the programmable mechanisms to be deployed, and their deployment, as programmable enablers in the resource to be protected to the Security Service Orchestrator. 6. The RR execute the Playbook and provide enforcement configuration to the SSO.

Dependencies	Security mechanisms, RR, CMR, SIEM, AI-driven SO, SSO
KPIs	Security service provisioning at three levels including application, cloud and infrastructure.
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	Increased visibility over the security metrics used for threat detection & classification and decision making. Tighter enforcement with limited overhead.

Table 3-11. UC3-Scenario 1 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofing	6G network monitoring service, 6G network interface, operational service interface	An attacker could try to spoof the identity of legitimate monitoring enablers to feed false security metrics and evade detection.	High
	Network Infrastructure	Attackers gaining unauthorized access to network devices or systems by impersonating legitimate users or devices, disrupting network operations.	
	Programmable Security Services	Attackers using stolen credentials can mislead AI systems, causing incorrect security decisions or alerts.	
Tampering	CTI databases, AI-enabled security orchestration, Security enabler catalogue, contextual data collected by AI-driven security decision module.	An attacker could attempt to tamper with the security enabler catalogue to remove or weaken certain detection and mitigation mechanisms.	High
		Compromised authentication mechanisms could allow attackers to manipulate security policies or evade security measures. An attacker could attempt to tamper with the contextual data collected by the AI-driven security decision module.	
Repudiation	6G network interface, operational service interface	A malicious network service provider could deny intentionally deploying a vulnerable service.	High
Information Disclosure	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms	An attacker could try to gain unauthorized access to the security metrics and contextual data collected, potentially revealing sensitive information.	High
Denial of Service	6G network, operational service, iTrust6G platform, Security Service Orchestrator (SSO) AI-driven Security Decision Modules	An attacker could attempt to overwhelm the monitoring enablers or SIEM with a flood of data to disrupt threat detection	High
		Overloading network components with traffic, leading to service disruptions and degraded performance.	
		Exhaustion of orchestrator resources, hindering the ability to deploy or manage security services. Overwhelmed with false positives or excessive traffic, potentially leading to failures in threat detection and response.	
Elevation of Privilege	Operational service interface, iTrust6G platform, AI-enabled security orchestration,	An attacker could seek to gain privileged access to the AI-driven security decision module to control remediation actions.	Critical

Table 3-12. UC3-Scenario 2 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Dynamic trust evaluation
Rational/Objective	This scenario evaluates the dynamic assessment and re-assessment of trust in various programmable network resources.
Stakeholders' roles	The Developer of a programmable security mechanism defines and implement the access to several metrics from a network service serving trust evaluation. The Network Service Provider operates network services that require dynamic trust

	<p>evaluations, and necessitates as per the agreement with other service provider and its customers to maintain a certain degree of trust.</p> <p>The Infrastructure Provider hosts and manages the resources that need trust evaluations.</p> <p>The attacker is willing to exploit a vulnerability directly affecting a network service, or indirectly by exploiting a weakness in the software dependencies or in the infrastructure. The risk or effective detection of its activity toward a network service represents a loss of trust.</p>
Pre-conditions	<p>Network services are operational and are programmed with adequate mechanism for trust evaluation.</p> <p>Contextual and behavioural data is available for trust assessments.</p>
Procedure/workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The programmable trust evaluation mechanisms collect contextual and behavioural data from network services. 2. The data are analysed to assess the current trust levels of various entities and services by the trust analyser. 3. Any changes in trust levels trigger an action from the PEP and RR. <p>Trust evaluations are continuously updated based on new data and interactions.</p>
Dependencies	Trust evaluation mechanisms, contextual data sources, network services
Envisioned architectural functionality	Real-time trust assessment and dynamic adjustment of security policies based on trust levels.
KPIs	Accuracy and timeliness of trust evaluations.
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	<p>Enhanced security through continuous and dynamic trust assessments.</p> <p>Improved adaptability to changing security contexts.</p>

Table 3-13. UC3-Scenario 2 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofting	6G network interface, operational service interface, Trust Evaluation Mechanisms	An attacker could try to spoof the identity of legitimate network services or data sources to feed false contextual and behavioural data to the trust evaluation mechanisms, manipulating the assessed trust levels.	High
Tampering	Contextual data sources, trust evaluation mechanisms, Policy Enforcement Point (PEP), Remediation Recommender (RR)	An attacker could attempt to tamper with the contextual and behavioural data collected by the trust evaluation mechanisms or manipulate the trust analysis process itself to influence the resulting trust levels and triggered actions.	High
Repudiation	6G network interface, operational service interface Monitoring and SIEM Systems AI-driven Security Decision Modules	<p>A malicious Network Service Provider or Infrastructure Provider could deny actions or events that impact the trustworthiness of their services, evading accountability.</p> <p>Attackers removing or altering logs to avoid detection, compromising the system's ability to trace and audit malicious activities.</p> <p>Tampered logs or data can mislead AI systems, resulting in incorrect trust evaluations and inappropriate security actions.</p>	Medium
Information Disclosure	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms	An attacker could seek to gain unauthorized access to the sensitive contextual and behavioural data collected for trust assessments, potentially revealing confidential information about the services and entities being evaluated.	Medium
Denial of Service	6G network, operational service, iTrust6G platform, PEP, RR	An attacker could attempt to disrupt the trust evaluation process by overwhelming the data collection, analysis, or policy enforcement components with excessive traffic or	High

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
		computationally intensive tasks.	
Elevation of Privilege	Operational service interface, iTrust6G platform, PEP, RR	An attacker could seek to gain unauthorized privileged access to the trust evaluation mechanisms, PEP, or RR components to manipulate trust levels or control the resulting security policy adjustments.	Critical

Table 3-14. UC3-Scenario 3 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Generation of threat intelligence
Rational/Objective	This scenario focuses on the creation and dissemination of threat intelligence to enhance the overall security posture.
Stakeholders' roles	The application developers create programmable resources gathering the necessary metrics serving threat Intelligence generation. The Network Service Providers operate network services embedding a programmable service, potentially generating TI. Infrastructure Providers support network service operation, The attacker conducts an activity scrutinised by security monitoring.
Pre-conditions	Programmable security mechanisms conducting security monitoring are in place. An attacker launches a technique recognised by the security monitoring tools.
Procedure/workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The activity of the attacker is followed by monitoring tools. 2. The programmable monitoring tools extract metrics, used by the by the security threat detection components. 3. The data are used by detection model for certain cyberthreats. 4. The data are aggregated and correlated according to an external cybersecurity CTI referential. 5. The data are correlated and the detected techniques is share as sharable CTI artefact.
Dependencies	Threat intelligence generation mechanisms, data sources, dissemination channels
Envisioned architectural functionality	Efficient collection, analysis, and sharing of threat intelligence to pre-empt and mitigate threats.
KPIs	Timeliness and accuracy of threat intelligence.
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	Enhanced collaboration and information sharing among stakeholders.

Table 3-15. UC3-Scenario 3 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofing	6G network interface, operational service interface, threat detection mechanisms.	An attacker could try to spoof the identity of legitimate monitoring tools or data sources to feed false security metrics and manipulate the threat intelligence generation process.	High
Tampering	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms, threat detection mechanisms, threat generation mechanisms.	An attacker could attempt to tamper with the security monitoring tools, detection models, or the threat intelligence generation process itself to manipulate the resulting threat intelligence artifacts.	High
Repudiation	6G network interface, operational service interface	An attacker could deny conducting the malicious activity that was detected by the security monitoring tools, or a service/infrastructure provider could deny the presence of a vulnerability or threat in their systems.	Medium
Information	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform	An attacker could seek to gain unauthorized	High

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Disclosure	security mechanisms, security threat detection components, threat intelligence generation mechanisms, dissemination channels Programmable Security Services Data Plane Resources Context Manager Repository (CMR)	access to the security metrics, detection models, or generated threat intelligence artifacts, potentially revealing sensitive information about the organization's security posture and vulnerabilities. Unauthorized access to sensitive security configurations and policies, leading to potential exploitation of known security mechanisms. Exfiltration of critical data stored or transmitted within the data plane, compromising the confidentiality of the information. Unauthorized access to context data, potentially leaking sensitive operational or security information.	
Denial of Service	6G network, operational service, iTrust6G platform	An attacker could attempt to disrupt the threat intelligence generation process by overwhelming the security monitoring tools, detection models, or analysis components with excessive traffic or computationally intensive tasks.	Medium
Elevation of Privilege	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms, security threat detection components, threat intelligence generation mechanisms, dissemination channels	An attacker could seek to gain unauthorized privileged access to the security monitoring tools, detection models, or threat intelligence generation mechanisms to manipulate the process or exfiltrate sensitive data.	High

Table 3-16. UC3-Scenario 4 Regular Description

Scenario Name	Proactive risk mitigation
Rational/Objective	This scenario aims to identify and mitigate risks before they can impact network services by enforcing playbook from TI.
Stakeholders' roles	The network service provider is willing to lower its risk exposure by proactively enforcing playbooks before incident time. The infrastructure operates network service for the network service providers, The attacker has conducted attacker an analogous service, and has his modus operandi analysed and proactive action mitigated via playbooks.
Pre-conditions	Risk identification and analysis mechanisms are operational. Network services are continuously monitored for potential risks. Mitigation measures are available for deployment.
Procedure/workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A remediation playbook is shared from another service provider and is received. 2. The remediation is checked and executed by the RR. 3. Additional security mechanisms are selected and deployed by the orchestrators. 4. The deployed mechanism is afterwards configured via their programmability interface.
Dependencies	mitigation measures security orchestrator, RR
Envisioned architectural functionality	Continuous risk assessment and proactive deployment of mitigation measures to ensure network resilience.
KPIs	Security service provisioning at three levels including application, cloud and infrastructure. Auto-reconfigurability of security measures in presence of an attack predicted/detected

	maintaining security policy compliance
Benefits of iTrust6G approach	Reduced risk impact through proactive identification and mitigation. Enhanced network resilience and security posture.

Table 3-17. UC3-Scenario 4 Threat Modelling

Type (STRIDE)	Components	Description	Qualitative Severity
Spoofing	6G network interface, operational service interface, remediation playbooks.	An attacker could attempt to spoof the identity of a legitimate network service or monitoring tool to evade detection or trigger false remediation actions.	High
Tampering	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security orchestrators, remediation playbooks. Data Plane Resources Security Service Orchestrator (SSO) Context Manager Repository (CMR)	An attacker could try to tamper with the risk identification process, remediation playbooks, or the deployment of mitigation measures to bypass or weaken the proactive security controls. Modification of data being transmitted or stored, potentially causing service disruptions or data corruption. Altered orchestrator commands or configurations, leading to incorrect deployment or management of security services. Corruption of context data, leading to inaccurate security assessments or responses.	High
Repudiation	6G network interface, operational service interface.	A malicious actor could deny conducting an attack that was detected and mitigated by the proactive risk mitigation system, making it difficult to attribute and respond to the incident.	Medium
Information Disclosure	Operational service data, iTrust6G platform security mechanisms, remediation playbooks.	An attacker could seek to gain unauthorized access to sensitive information about identified risks, remediation playbooks, or deployed mitigation measures, potentially exposing vulnerabilities or enabling them to circumvent security controls.	High
Denial of Service	6G network, operational service, iTrust6G platform, security orchestrators.	An attacker could attempt to overwhelm the risk identification process, security orchestrators, or deployed mitigation measures with excessive traffic or requests, disrupting the proactive risk mitigation capabilities.	High
Elevation of Privilege	Operational service interface, iTrust6G platform, security orchestrators. Network Infrastructure Programmable Security Services AI-driven Security Decision Modules	An attacker could seek to gain unauthorized privileged access to the risk identification systems, remediation playbooks, or security orchestrators to manipulate the proactive risk mitigation process or deploy malicious mitigation measures. Exploiting vulnerabilities to gain higher access levels, potentially compromising entire network segments. Unauthorized elevation of privileges within security services, allowing attackers to bypass security controls. Elevated privileges can lead to unauthorized modifications of AI models or decision-making processes, undermining the integrity of security decisions.	High

4 Requirements

Requirements elicitation is the process of gathering the requirements of a system from users, stakeholders, and other sources. The IEEE provides a standard for Software Requirements Specifications (SRS), which is a comprehensive description of the intended purpose and environment for software under development. [14]

IEEE Standard 830-199 8: This standard outlines the recommended practices for writing an SRS. It includes the following sections:

- **Introduction:** Purpose, scope, definitions, references, and overview of the SRS.
- **General Description:** Product perspective, product functions, user characteristics, constraints, and assumptions.
- **Specific Requirements:** Detailed requirements, including functional requirements, external interface requirements, performance requirements, design constraints, and attributes such as security, maintainability, and portability.

4.1 Requirement types

According to the IEEE standard [14], system requirements can be classified as:

Functional Requirement (FUN). It is a requirement that specifies a function that a system, or system component, must be able to perform. A requirement specifying what the overall system, or a specific component, will be able to do. Statements of services that the system should provide, how the system should react to inputs and how the system should behave in different situations. Among the functional requirements are also included security requirements relating to the security services offered by the system to users or other systems.

Non-functional Requirement (NOF). It is a requirement specifying how the system or component will implement its functionality. In this document the following non-functional types of requirements are considered:

- **Design Requirement (DCC):** a requirement that specifies or constraints the design of a system or system component. A design constraint requirement defines the limits on the options of a solution that are available to a designer; for example, to use a specific technology, product, or the adoption of a specific technical standard.
- **Implementation Requirement (IMP):** a requirement that specifies or constrains the coding or construction of a system or system component.
- **Interface Requirement (INT):** a requirement that specifies an external item with which a system or system component must interact, or that sets forth constraints on formats, timing, or other factors caused by such an interaction.
- **Security Requirement (SEC):** a requirement specifying security-related aspects, that is how the system secures itself (security functions that the system provides to users or other systems, or infrastructures are to be considered functional requirements).
- **Operating Requirement (OPR):** a requirement defining the operational conditions or properties that are required for the system to operate or exist. This type of requirement includes human factors, ergonomics, availability, maintainability, reliability.
- **Legal Requirement (LEG):** a requirement defining the conditions or properties necessary for the component or the system to conform to national or international law and regulations.

- **Usability Requirement (USA):** a requirement defining expectations and specifications designed to ensure that the component and/or system or environment is easy to use.

Given the eminent research nature of the iTrust6G project, requirements must focus on the evaluation and demonstration of the project technical proposals, with the goal of providing proofs of the suitability of such proposals to the project objectives, connecting them with the proposed KPIs. Project results will eventually be incorporated into actual products as part of further innovation activity after the end of the project, but these products as such are not part of project goals. Therefore, the requirements analysed here are basically of the functional and non-functional types, as they constitute the scope of a research action like iTrust6G.

In the following sections, a definition of the scope of iTrust6G requirements is given, together with a formal description of those requirements, divided between the general requirements for security frameworks applicable to next-generation networks and the specific requirements applicable to the concrete technologies considered by the project.

4.2 Common characteristics and scope

During the analysis of requirements, the project team has identified a set of characteristics common to any application of the technologies considered as target of iTrust6G. While these characteristics cannot formally be considered as requirements, it is important to note them in order to provide an appropriate scope for the description of general and specific requirements discussed in the following sections.

These general characteristics include:

- The application of zero-trust principles, continuously monitoring and evaluating any communication between network elements, and comparing them to established baselines for the normal behaviour of users, devices and network functions.
- The monitoring of the status and performance of the framework services.
- The proper management of vulnerabilities, security incidents and remediation actions. This includes appropriate scan and update measures, the collection of relevant data and logs, and the generation of reports able to support friendly UX systems for users and administrators.
- Security orchestration mechanisms able to manage, coordinate, and automate the deployment, configuration, and operation of network services, functions, and resources in a secure manner, addressing threat remediation by means of security controls configuration interfaces, of programmatic nature. These orchestration mechanisms shall support robust automation capabilities, be fine-tuneable to accommodate business logic constraints, and support customization, extension, and integration with third-party tools, scripts, and plugins.
- The operation of the security framework effectively ensuring key requirements of 6G, such as energy efficiency and pervasiveness.

4.3 General requirements

The following requirements have been identified as associated with the application of enhanced security services in next-generation networks in general. Table 4-1 presents, for each requirement, its identifier (with the “FUN” prefix for functional requirements, and “NOF” for non-functional requirements), the framework capabilities related to it, a description, the means for its verification, and the project KPI(s) related to the requirement.

Table 4-1. General Requirements

Requirement ID	Related Capabilities	Description	Verifiability	Related KPI(s)
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_001	Data Plane Security Operations	Support secure communication channels with strong encryption protocols between devices and backend systems to prevent data leakage and protect against eavesdropping and unauthorized access	Software	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2 KPI-O3.4
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_002	Data Plane Security Operations	Integrate authentication, monitoring and attestation methods for devices to ensure only authorized users and devices can access the network.	Software	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2 KPI-O3.4 KPI-O6.9 KPI-6.10
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_003	Security Monitoring Data Plane Control Plane	Apply zero-trust principles by: (i) Continuously monitoring and evaluating the security posture of operated assets. (ii) Regularly assessing the integrity of the underlying infrastructure.	Demonstrator	KPI-O2-1 KPI-O2-5 KPI-O3.4
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_004	Control Plane Security Operations	Apply strong encryption in all management and orchestration channels, and any other side channel in use	Software	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2 KPI-O3.4
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_005	Risk Management Threat Detection Security Operations	Provide collaborative risk management, threat detection, and cyber threat intelligence generation across multi-tenant environments.	Demonstrator	KPI-O2-1 KPI-O2-2 KPI-O2-3 KPI-O2-4 KPI-O2-5 KPI-O4-3 KPI-O4-4 KPI-O4-5
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_006	Threat Reporting and Alerting SIEM	Provide near real-time alerts for critical threats and potential security incidents	Demonstrator	KPI-O2-3 KPI-O2-4 KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2 KPI-O6.4 KPI-O6.5 KPI-O6.6 KPI-O6.7 KPI-O6.8
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_007	SIEM	Support interactive and dynamic visualization of the generated timelines, allowing correlation between events, zoom into specific time periods, and directly link each event to its source	Demonstrator	KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_008	SIEM	Support the processing of large volumes of diverse digital evidence data	Software	KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_009	Infrastructure	Enable programmatic security orchestration across multiple domains in a 6G environment	Demonstrator	KPI-O2-1 KPI-O2-2 KPI-O2-5
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_010	Security Operations	Security controls re-configurations should not require downtime	Demonstrator	KPI-O4-4 KPI-O4-5 KPI-O6.5
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_011	Federated Learning Infrastructure	The system shall be developed using frameworks suitable for federated learning, and support their execution on	Software	KPI-O2-1 KPI-O2-5 KPI-O3.1

Requirement ID	Related Capabilities	Description	Verifiability	Related KPI(s)
		edge devices in cooperation with secure central servers		
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_012	Data Plane Control Plane Security Operations	Crypto functionalities will allow the use quantum-resistant algorithms and protocols unless not allowed by underlying hardware / software limitations	Software	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_013	Attestation Trust Management	Provide an attestation framework to allow monitoring of the integrity for each registered entity	Demonstrator	KPI-O3.3
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_014	Attestation Trust Management	The attestation framework shall emit a trust posture regarding all elements that should be scalable and integrable with other components	Software	KPI-O3.3
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_015	Attestation Trust Management	The system should be able to establish the trustworthiness of software packages by analysing the security posture of the different components of the package, i.e., libraries, used open-source code, dependencies.	Software	KPI-O3.3 KPI-O6.1
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_016	Risk Management Security Operations Security by design	Apply a risk model to manage risks in security domains. Each resource in the network should be mapped into the model according to its characteristics and relation to other resources, pervasively integrating security mechanism within the service design	Document	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2 KPI-O5.1 KPI-O5.2 KPI-O6.6 KPI-O6.7 KPI-O6.8
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_017	Risk Management Control Plane	Apply formal models to describe the managed networks and their automated configuration	Document	KPI-O4-3 KPI-O4-4 KPI-O4-5 KPI-O5.1 KPI-O5.2
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_018	Risk Management Security Operations	Apply formal models to describe the automated configuration of networks and security controls	Document	KPI-O4-3 KPI-O4-4 KPI-O4-5 KPI-O5.1 KPI-O5.2

4.4 Specific Requirements

The following requirements have been identified as associated with the use of the specific technologies iTrust6G is committed to evaluate, develop and apply to enhance security services in next-generation networks. Table 4-2 presents, for each requirement, its identifier (with the “FUN” prefix for functional requirements, and “NOF” for non-functional requirements), the framework capabilities related to it, a description, the means for its verification, and the project KPI(s) related to the requirement.

Table 4-2. Specific Requirements

Requirement ID	Related Capabilities	Description	Verifiability	Related KPI(s)
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_001	Security Monitoring	Employ AI and deep learning algorithms for trust inference that can detect malicious packets and anomalous network traffic patterns, suitable for identifying zero-day	Software	KPI-O2-2 KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2 KPI-O6.1

Requirement ID	Related Capabilities	Description	Verifiability	Related KPI(s)
		attacks by utilizing various data features as input		KPI-O6.4 KPI-O6.6 KPI-O6.9
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_002	Security Operations	Provide means to quarantine compromised devices, network infrastructures and functions	Demonstrator	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2 KPI-O3.4 KPI-O4.3 KPI-O6.9 KPI-6.10
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_003	Security Operations	Support and provide evidence of all devices, network infrastructures and functions regarding their software and firmware updates.	Demonstrator	KPI-O3.2 KPI-O3.3 KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_004	Security Operations Data plane	Provide methods to securely track and monitor network paths and assess their trustworthiness	Demonstrator	KPI-O3.2 KPI-O3.3 KPI-O3.4 KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_005	Data Analysis Trust Management	Automatically aggregate and correlate disparate sources of temporal data and digital traces	Demonstrator	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2 KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_006	Threat Remediation	Define a framework for sharing remediation playbooks in a standard format, enabling proactive threat mitigation among tenants and with external platforms.	Document	KPI-O2-2 KPI-O2-3 KPI-O5.1 KPI-O5.2
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_007	Threat Intelligence	Integrate threat intelligence into the zero-trust architecture. Gather data from deployed ML models to improving threat detection and remediation approaches. Correlate detected threats with widely known vulnerabilities (e.g.: CVEs)	Demonstrator	KPI-O2-4 KPI-O2-5 KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_008	Security Operations	Proactively propose remediations to improve the security posture of the managed network.	Demonstrator	KPI-O4-3 KPI-O4-4 KPI-O4-5 KPI-O6.2 KPI-O6.3 KPI-O6.5
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_009	Security Monitoring	Provide continuous trust evaluation and re-evaluation mechanisms for operational security of network services, computing resources, and users	Software	KPI-O3.1 KPI-O3.2 KPI-O4.1 KPI-O4.2 KPI-O6.9 KPI-6.10
iTrust6G_NOF_SP_010	Security Monitoring Management plane	Data objects will contain provenance elements, associated to the identity of their original sources and intermediate processors, to protect their integrity and allow consumers to assess their validity and timeliness	Software	KPI-O3.1
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_011	Security Monitoring	Collected data shall be properly managed through cleaning, normalisation and	Software	KPI-O2-1 KPI-O2-5

Requirement ID	Related Capabilities	Description	Verifiability	Related KPI(s)
	Management plane	transformation techniques.		
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_012	Federated Learning Management Plane	Secure aggregation algorithms and privacy-preservation model sharing shall be deployed in the Federated Learning system, ensuring user privacy	Software	KPI-03.1 KPI-04.1 KPI-05.1
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_013	Security Operations	Support the application of intent-based security policies, applied by means of explainable and automated end-to-end security orchestration	Software	KPI-03.1 KPI-04-3 KPI-04-4 KPI-04-5 KPI-05.1 KPI-05.2
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_014	Security Orchestrator	Provide secure service design and delivery through smart slice provisioning and network functions placement. Assure application access to them through language agnostic programmatic interfaces.	Software	KPI-03.4 KPI-04-3 KPI-04-4 KPI-04-5
iTrust6G_NOF_SP_015	Authentication and Authorization Trust Management	Access to all interfaces will be based on component and user identities, roles and attributes. Identities will be propagated across the components for this purpose	Software	KPI-03.1 KPI-03.4 KPI-05.1 KPI-05.2
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_016	Authentication and Authorization Control Plane Security Operations	All interfaces among the different components will apply token-based authentication and authorization, based on current standards	Software	KPI-03.1 KPI-03.4
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_017	Authentication and Authorization Trust Management	All interactions will be logged, for further accounting and/or auditing. Log entries will include identity properties used for authorization	Demonstrator	KPI-03.1 KPI-03.4 KPI-05.1 KPI-05.2
iTrust6G_NOF_SP_018	Hardware Attestation	Each entity shall equip a TPM for the attestation process to register the event measure, report the measures, and ensure device identity with supporting open-source software	Document	KPI-03.1 KPI-03.3
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_019	Security Management	Maintain a continuous non-real-time updated assessment of the risks in the system according to the risk model by gathering and processing threat intelligence coming from internal and external sources	Demonstrator	KPI-02-4 KPI-02-5
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_020	Security Management	Propose and evaluate remediations based on the mitigation impact according to the risk model	Software	KPI-02-5 KPI-04-3 KPI-04-4 KPI-04-5 KPI-05.1 KPI-05.2 KPI-06.6 KPI-06.7 KPI-06.8

5 Threat Modelling

The project aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the security risks in general for 6G networks and particularly for iTrust6G scenarios and use cases. The threat analysis will involve several key steps: asset discovery, vulnerability identification, and attack vector analysis. It will consider both internal and external threats, examining how insiders or external attackers might exploit vulnerabilities in the system.

iTrust6G aims to inspire threat analysis through well-known de facto standard categorisation and threat information sources. The most authoritative source for an EC-funded project is undoubtedly the ENISA, which produces essential reference documentation. In particular, the following analysis are performed:

- Threat Landscape Report (2023 version, the last one now of this document writing, and the previous ones) [15].
- Threat Landscape for 5G networks (the most tailored one to iTrust6G scenarios) [16].

However, since the aim is to increase this project's impact, we will also consider other de facto standards developed mainly at the US level. The most important is the MITRE ATT&CK, a knowledge base of adversary tactics and techniques based on real-world observations. This knowledge base has been extensively used as the foundation for specific threat models and methodologies in the private sector, government, and cybersecurity product and service community.

Moreover, ATT&CK is integrated into a more complex ecosystem to provide public information about cybersecurity. Indeed, In iTrust6G, adopting precise and well-recognised frameworks for threat analysis ensures the validity of the approach, the extensibility of the results, and a greater impact.

We will also consider:

- The MITRE D3FEND framework, which complements the ATT&CK framework with knowledge about countermeasures to attacks, defensive techniques, and strategies. It uses the concept of digital artifact to map the two.
- The Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) system provides a reference method for publicly known information-security vulnerabilities and exposures.
- The Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) provides a score (in the 0-10 range) to evaluate and rank reported vulnerabilities in a standardised, repeatable, and vendor-agnostic way.
- The Exploit Prediction Scoring System (EPSS) provides a score for estimating the likelihood (probability) that a software vulnerability will be exploited in the wild. EPSS uses current threat information from CVE and real-world exploit data to produce a probability score that a vulnerability will be exploited.

In this project, the threat analysis will also serve to model risks in the use cases; they will be used to elicit trust key performance indicators (see Section 6).

5.1 Threat actors

Threat actors are individuals or groups that intentionally threaten digital devices or systems. Threat actors may perform different malicious operations on computer systems, such as exploiting vulnerabilities in computer systems, networks, and software, mounting cyberattacks, including phishing, ransomware, and malware attacks, and disrupting operations.

According to IBM and US Government documents (e.g., NIST), there are many categories of threat actors, all with different motivations, educational backgrounds, skills, resources, targets, and uses of stolen data and compromised resources. They include the following:

- Hacktivists use their skills to promote political, social, or ideological agendas. Hacktivists typically target organisations, governments, or corporations they perceive as corrupt, oppressive, or unjust. They are not driven by personal gain. They typically target their victim reputation: they deface websites, launch distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks, and leak and share victim's sensitive information.
- Nation-state actors / State-nexus threat groups are cyber threat actors that operate with the support, direction, or approval of a nation-state. These groups perform espionage, sabotage, cyber warfare, and disruptive operations targeting other nations, critical infrastructure, and state-sensitive private entities, aligning their activities with the strategic objectives of their sponsoring government.
- Cybercriminals are individuals or groups who commit illegal activities for financial gain. Their attack includes hacking, identity theft, ransomware attacks, and fraud. They exploit vulnerabilities in systems and networks to steal data, disrupt services, or extort victims. Moreover, they use all the social engineering techniques to force humans to make mistakes that allow them to compromise computer systems.
- Thrill seekers are individuals who engage in hacking or other cyber activities for excitement and challenge rather than for financial gain or ideological reasons. They are motivated by the satisfaction of overcoming technical obstacles and increasing their fame.
- Insider threat actors are individuals within an organisation, such as employees, contractors, or business partners, who misuse their authorised access to harm the organisation's systems, data, or operations. They can perform intentional or unintentional actions; their motivations may be personal gain, revenge, or negligence.
- Cyberterrorists are individuals or groups that use cyber-attacks to intimidate or coerce governments, organisations, or societies for political, ideological, or religious goals. As all the terrorists, their actions are driven to create fear, disrupt critical infrastructures, and cause harm or chaos. and
- Hackers-for-hire are individuals or groups who are paid for their hacking skills and services. These hackers can be contracted to perform various activities, including cyber espionage, data theft, system infiltration, and disruption of services, often for financial gain or specific objectives dictated by their clients.

Knowing and understanding different types of threat actors is critical for defining the protections and mitigations against the risks they introduce.

5.2 Taxonomy

We will adopt the MITRE ATT&CK knowledge base as iTrust6G threats and attacks reference taxonomy.

ATT&CK is a comprehensive framework for understanding adversarial tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) used in cyber-attacks. ATT&CK is continuously updated with contributions from cybersecurity professionals worldwide, ensuring relevance, comprehensiveness, and timeliness.

It provides an extensive Knowledge Base that categorises real-world adversary behaviour, detailing the specific techniques attackers use across various attack steps.

Attackers and their behaviours are modelled through their Tactics and Techniques. Tactics represent the motivations for a threat actor to conduct attacks. It is the adversary's tactical goal: the reason for performing an action. Tactics are, hence, a categorisation of the attacker's goals. The current model lists 14 Tactics. Techniques are, instead, the methods attacker may use to achieve their goals. Techniques can be combined to model more sophisticated attacker strategies.

Both Tactics and Techniques are categorised by three scenarios: Enterprise, Mobile, and Industrial Control Systems (ICS). For instance, the Tactics by scenario are:

- Enterprise: Reconnaissance, Resource Development, Initial Access, Execution, Persistence, Privilege Escalation, Defence Evasion, Credential Access, Discovery, Lateral Movement, Collection, Command and Control, Exfiltration, Impact;
- Mobile: Initial Access, Execution, Persistence, Privilege Escalation, Defence Evasion, Credential Access, Discovery, Lateral Movement, Collection, Command and Control, Exfiltration, Impact, Network Effects, Remote Service Effects;
- ICS: Initial Access, Execution, Persistence, Privilege Escalation, Evasion, Discovery, Lateral Movement, Collection Command and Control, Inhibit Response Function, Impair Process Control, Impact.

Data about Tactics and Techniques are easily organised and visualised using the ATT&CK Matrix. The Matrix has already been designed to divide elements according to the Platforms. Indeed, ATT&CK covers a wide range of platforms: Windows, macOS, Linux, Cloud, Network, Containers and preparation techniques, which can be easily filtered through the Matrix.

ATT&CK can be used to simulate attacks and to assess and improve their defences. Indeed, it also offers a section on detection techniques and mitigation strategies to counteract identified techniques.

ATT&CK facilitates threat intelligence sharing, enhances incident response, and supports the development of robust security measures by aligning defence strategies with observed attacker behaviours.

5.3 Attack vectors

Attack vectors are the means used by attackers to enter a network or system. While this information is not directly included in the ATT&CK framework, attack vectors can be interesting in determining an organization's attack exposure. They show another interesting perspective to the threat analysis. Attack vectors include social engineering attacks, credential theft, vulnerability exploits, and insufficient protection against insider threats; they overlap partially with ATT&CK information.

Computer systems application environments are extremely complex, and their services need to be shared (e.g., for business purposes). Therefore, closing the attack vectors is not suitable. However, identifying and limiting them is essential.

In this context, vulnerabilities play an important role. Handling them properly to reduce their exploitability and patching them to make them unusable for attackers is a crucial task for information security. The ENISA has proposed a framework¹, largely inspired by the NIST IR 8011 series² (Vulnerability management). Moreover, we mention the NIST SP 800 40rev3³ (Enterprise Patch Management).

5.4 Mitigations

Mitigations are not the primary objective of a threat analysis. However, we mention here the MITRE D3FEND framework⁴, the NIST SP 800-53rev5 series⁵. It is worth noting that an initiative proposed a mapping between MITRE ATT&CK® and NIST Special Publication 800-53⁶. The MITRE D3FEND framework facilitates the mapping

¹ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/training-and-exercises/trainings-for-cybersecurity-specialists/online-training-material/documents/vulnerability-handling-handbook>

² https://csrc.nist.gov/glossary/term/vulnerability_management

³ <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/40/r4/final>

⁴ <https://d3fend.mitre.org/>

⁵ <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/53/r5/upd1/final>

⁶ <https://mitre-engenuity.org/cybersecurity/center-for-threat-informed-defense/our-work/nist-800-53-control-mappings/>

of attack patterns, as described and categorized by the ATT&CK framework, to defensive techniques. These mappings allow for pinpointing the most plausible threats to a system, or the most significant ones, based on risk scores and the availability of security controls capable of countering specific attack techniques.

By leveraging these frameworks, it is possible to integrate additional prioritization mechanisms in threat analysis. This approach considers not only the attacker's perspective, focusing on understanding the attacks and their perpetrators, but also the defence apparatus that should counter and mitigate these threats.

Until now, the lack of systematic efforts in this direction has hindered the development of practical solutions for integrating this approach into threat analysis. The absence of common abstractions and structures among various corpuses and knowledge bases has been a significant barrier. Additionally, it is important to note the relative recency of these initiatives. Therefore, their actual impact will become evident only over time.

6 Trust Key Performance Indicators

In this section, we list the different key performance indicators identified in the previous sections of this document and justify them according to the conducted threat analysis. We classify the different indicators based on their source:

- The indicators defined in iTrust6G's concept and technical objectives, in charge of evaluating the implementation of general and specific requirements;
- The indicators provided in the definition of the use cases scenarios, to gauge the technical advancement of the project beyond the state-of-the-art and their ability to satisfy business cases;

The threat analysis conducted on the use case implementation, to validate the robustness of the platform design. Table 6-1 lists the different identified key performance indicators.

Table 6-1. KPIs

ID	KPI	Description	Target	Source
KPI-O1.1	Support for infrastructure resources requirements	The delivered system architecture fully supports the services and infrastructure resources requirements of proposed use cases. Number of unsupported services.	0	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O1.2	Adequacy of the trust models	Each one of the three use case families rely on a trust model aligned with the architecture exposing a set of stakeholders, their trust relations, and the properties provided by the architecture serving their continuous trust evaluation. Trust failures in use cases.	0	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O1.3	Risk & threat detection & mitigation	The architecture covers the detection and the mitigation of the risks and threats determined by three use case families, covering distinct types of resources deployed on the cloud continuum. Percentage of mitigated threats against configured protections.	99%	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O2-1	Security Monitoring Compatibility	The proposed monitoring services apply to different types of resources operated by the use cases. Percentage of monitored services resources.	99%	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O2-2	Cyber-threat reporting	Threats showcased in the use case are detected, qualified, and reported through cyber-threat intelligence. Percentage of threats reports to CTI system.	99%	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O2-3	Mean time for CTI sharing	A generated cyber-threat intelligence is shared and starts to be enacted in less than 1 minute. Timespan between receiving a new CTI and having protection against it activated.	1 min	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O2-4	Mean time for vulnerability assessment	The distributed vulnerability assessment framework covers different types of resources in a tenant and assesses vulnerability. Max duration to scan a given network service.	10 min	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O2-5	Referential in assurance conformity framework	Three different security referential are implemented by the assurance conformity framework. Number of critical systems and data assets with defined security referentials.	3	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O3.1	Trust model compatibility	The proposed trust model applies to the three different use cases. Average percentage of coverage for trust models in the use cases.	100%	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O3.2	Support for dependencies repository	The trust management system infers trust from three different dependencies repository type for all the use case applications. Minimum repositories sources for	3	Technical Objectives (Section 2)

ID	KPI	Description	Target	Source
		trust inference.		
KPI-O3.3	Mean time to tampered node detection	Time it takes remote attestation engine identifies tampered node resource and network services instances.	1 min	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O3.4	Mean time to access control decision	Max delay when the accesses control monitor provides an access decision to a network slice.	1 sec	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O4.1	Number of monitored class of resources	Number of monitored different classes of resources building the 6G platforms.	5	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O4.2	Threat detection	Types of threats in different use cases that are detected.	10	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O4.3	Performance of security enablers selection	Time it takes the selection of pertinent security enablers to mitigate an identified threat.	1 min	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O4.4	Security programmability overhead	Programmability-induced performance degradation on key use case metrics is under X%.	5%	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O4.5	Security programmability performance	The programmability models permit reconfiguration in less than X seconds in most cases, and the injection of arbitrary logic in less than Y seconds in the different use cases.	10 sec 60 sec	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O5.1	Policy format applicability	Number of use case families that have successfully specified their 6G applications and trust model using the policy formats.	3	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-O5.2	Performance of policy interpretability	The policies are interpreted into technical directives in a reasonable time. Delay in seconds to interpret policies.	10 sec	Technical Objectives (Section 2)
KPI-UC1-1.1	Cloud-native service deployment	Time for cloud-native service reconfiguration in edge-cloud continuum.	10 min	Use case 1 (Section 3.4.1)
KPI-UC1-1.2	Cloud-native service reconfiguration	Time for cloud-native service deployment in edge-cloud continuum	10 min	Use case 1 (Section 3.4.1)
KPI-UC1-1.3	Impact of cloud-native service reconfiguration	Performance degradation of cloud-native service reconfiguration in edge-cloud continuum.	10%	Use case 1 (Section 3.4.1)
KPI-UC1-2.1	VNF-based service deployment	Time for VNF-based network service deployment.	1 min	Use case 1 (Section 3.4.1)
KPI-UC1-2.2	VNF-based* service reconfiguration	Time for VNF-based network service reconfiguration.	1 min	Use case 1 (Section 3.4.1)
KPI-UC2-1.1	Attack reaction delay	Attack detection and mitigation delay with 2 or more concurrent attacks.	1 min	Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-1.2	Threat prediction	Percentage of variant/mutated threat prediction based on the forensics analysis of the previous attack.	75%	Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.1	Duration of trust duration	Time for re-establishing trust chain after compromise.	2 min	Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.2	Trust Re-establishment Delay (TRD)t	This metric measures the variation in a key QoS metric, such as service availability or response time, caused by the need to re-establish trust after a security	100 ms	Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)

ID	KPI	Description	Target	Source
		compromise or failure in the trust chain.		
KPI-UC2-2.3	Compliance preservation	Percentage of compliance preservation during the trust chain re-establishment after compromise.	50%	Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC3-1.1	Number of programmability levels for threat incident handling	Security service provisioning at three levels including application, cloud and infrastructure.	3	Use case 3 (Section 3.4.3)
KPI-UC3-2.1	Performance of trust evaluation	Accuracy and timeliness of trust evaluations.	95%	Use case 3 (Section 3.4.3)
KPI-UC3-2.2	Overhead of the trust evaluation	Variation on the Quality of Service and Security indicators	15%	Use case 3 (Section 3.4.3)
KPI-UC3-3.1	Performance of generated TI	Duration and accuracy of threat intelligence	<1 sec 95% accurate	Use case 3 (Section 3.4.3)
KPI-UC3-3.2	Mean-time to enforcement of shared TI	Duration of set-up threat mitigation based on shared intelligence.	1 min	Use case 3 (Section 3.4.3)
KPI-UC3-4.1	Number of programmability levels for risk mitigation	Security service provisioning at three levels including application, cloud and infrastructure.	3	Use case 3 (Section 3.4.3)
KPI-UC3-4.2	Performance of Auto-reconfigurability of security measures	Duration of Auto-reconfigurability of security measures in presence of an attack predicted/detected while maintaining security policy compliance	2 minutes	Use case 3 (Section 3.4.3)
KPI-UC1-1.1	Cloud-native service deployment	Time for cloud-native service reconfiguration in edge-cloud continuum	10 min	Use case 1 (Section 3.4.1)
KPI-UC2-1.S	Exposure to Spoofing threat in UC2 scenario 1	Numbers of entities from iTrust6G platform vulnerable to be impersonated	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-1.T	Exposure to Tampering threat in UC2 scenario 1	Number of data channels vulnerable to tampering between the platform and security controls.	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-1.R	Exposure to Repudiation threat in UC2 scenario 1	Number of activities not subjected to audit records	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-1.I	Exposure to Information disclosure threat in UC2 scenario 1	Number of sensitive information from iTrust6G platform accessible from compromised network services	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-1.D	Exposure to Denial-of-service threat in UC2 scenario 1	Number of iTrust6G platform component without DoS countermeasures	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-1.E	Exposure to Privilege Escalation threat in UC2 scenario 1	Number of iTrust6G privileged account exposed from compromised network services	1	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.S	Exposure to Spoofing threat in	Numbers of entities involved in trust assessment from iTrust6G platform vulnerable to impersonation	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2

ID	KPI	Description	Target	Source
	UC2 scenario 2			(Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.T	Exposure to Tampering threat in UC2 scenario 2	Number of dataflows between iTrust6G component involved in trust assessment vulnerable to tampering	1	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.R	Exposure to Repudiation threat in UC2 scenario 2	Number of trust evaluation process steps not subjected to audit records	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.I	Exposure to Information disclosure threat in UC2 scenario 2	Number of unprotected and sensitive information involved in the trust assessment	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.D	Exposure to Denial-of-service threat in UC2 scenario 2	Number of iTrust6G platform component involved in trust assessment without DoS countermeasures	0	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)
KPI-UC2-2.E	Exposure to Privilege Escalation threat in UC2 scenario 2	Number of Exposed iTrust6G trust evaluation components exposed to compromised services	1	Threat Analysis Use case 2 (Section 3.4.2)

7 Traceability Matrix

A Requirements Traceability Matrix (RTM) is a document that links requirements throughout the validation process. The purpose of the RTM is to ensure that all requirements defined for the iTrust6G project are met, facilitates impact analysis for changes, and provides a clear linkage between requirements and their corresponding test cases. By maintaining an up-to-date RTM throughout the implementation of the project it will ensure that all requirements are accounted for and tested, ensuring that no functionality is missing or untested.

Table 7-1. Use cases, Scenarios, and Requirements

Requirements		UCs/Scenarios								Status
		UC-01: Dynamic security orchestration and trust establishment in multi-stakeholder and multi-domain environment		UC-02: Operational Security and Trust re-evaluation		UC-03: Programmable Security as a Service				
Req. ID	Requirement Type	Edge-cloud continuum and the use of cloud-native mechanisms	Dynamic provision of VNF	Back-to-back Distributed Attacks on an Operational Service	Trust Re-establishment in Case of Compromised Trust Chain	Threat detection and mitigation	Dynamic trust evaluation	Generation of Threat Intelligence	Proactive Risk mitigation	
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_001	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_002	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_003	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_004	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_005	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_006	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_007	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_008	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_009	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_010	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_011	General									Started
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_012	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_013	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_014	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_GEN_015	General									Started
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_016	General									Started
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_017	General									Started
iTrust6G_NOF_GEN_018	General									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_001	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_002	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_003	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_004	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_005	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_006	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_007	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_008	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_009	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_NOF_SP_010	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_011	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_012	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_013	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_014	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_NOF_SP_015	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_016	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_017	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_NOF_SP_018	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_019	Specific									Started
iTrust6G_FUN_SP_020	Specific									Started

8 Conclusions and Future Work

The iTrust6G project has made progress in defining use case requirements and conducting a comprehensive threat surface analysis for 6G networks. Through careful examination of potential scenarios and stakeholder needs, the project identified key areas where enhanced security and trust mechanisms are essential for the successful deployment and operation of 6G systems.

The iTrust6G project has made significant strides in its research and proof-of-concept efforts to enhance security and trust in 6G networks. Through a comprehensive analysis of use case requirements and potential threat surfaces, the project has identified critical areas where innovative security solutions are needed to ensure the successful deployment and operation of 6G systems. The use case analysis revealed the complex and multi-faceted nature of 6G networks, highlighting the need for dynamic security orchestration across multiple domains and stakeholders. The project's focus on zero-trust principles, AI-driven threat detection, and programmable security demonstrates a forward-thinking approach to addressing the unique challenges posed by the evolving telecommunications landscape.

The threat surface analysis conducted as part of this deliverable provides valuable insights into the potential vulnerabilities and attack vectors that networks may face. By leveraging established frameworks such as MITRE ATT&CK and incorporating emerging threat intelligence, iTrust6G has laid a solid foundation for specifying and creating proof-of-concepts of robust security measures tailored to the 6G environment.

The identification and documentation of specific requirements, both general and technology-specific, offer a clear roadmap to guide the concepts that are being investigated in iTrust6G WP3, WP4, and WP5 where the main components of iTrust6G's security framework will be produced. These requirements, aligned with project KPIs, ensure that the resulting solutions will meet the needs of various stakeholders while addressing critical security concerns. The project's emphasis on trust management and continuous re-evaluation of security postures aligns with the dynamic nature of 6G networks.

The trust algorithms and attestation mechanisms are promising in maintaining a high level of security even in complex, multi-tenant environments. Moving forward, the iTrust6G project will focus on translating the identified requirements and threat analysis into concrete technical solutions. This will involve the development and refinement of AI-driven security orchestration mechanisms, programmable security interfaces, and advanced trust evaluation algorithms.

Further research and development efforts will be directed towards enhancing the project's capabilities in areas such as federated learning for improved threat detection, quantum-resistant cryptography, and intent-based security policy enforcement. These advancements will be crucial in addressing emerging threats and ensuring the long-term viability of the iTrust6G framework. The project will prioritize the integration and validation of its security solutions within realistic 6G network environments. This will involve collaboration with industry partners and the establishment of testbeds to evaluate the effectiveness of iTrust6G's approaches under various operational scenarios. Identified requirements from this deliverable will frame the blueprinting activities of the platform, guiding the initial architecture design outlined in D2.2.

As the project progresses, there will be an increased focus on standardization efforts and alignment with evolving 6G specifications. iTrust6G will actively engage with relevant standards bodies and industry forums to ensure that its security innovations can be widely adopted and integrated into future 6G deployments. Finally, the project will continue to refine its KPIs and evaluation methodologies, incorporating feedback from stakeholders and lessons learned from initial implementations. This iterative process will be crucial in ensuring that iTrust6G delivers a comprehensive, adaptable, and effective security framework that meets the evolving needs of the 6G ecosystem.

Bibliography

- [1] D. Firesmith, "Use case modeling guidelines," in *Proceedings of Technology of Object-Oriented Languages and Systems - TOOLS 30 (Cat. No.PR00278)*, Santa Barbara CA, USA, 1999.
- [2] P. Scalise, M. Boeding, M. Hempel, H. Sharif, J. Delloiacovo and J. Reed, "A Systematic Survey on 5G and 6G Security Considerations, Challenges, Trends, and Research Areas," *Future Internet* 16, p. 16, 2024.
- [3] S. Abdel Hakeem, H. Hussein and H. Kim, "Security Requirements and Challenges of 6G Technologies and Applications," Basel, 2022.
- [4] 3GPP-SA2, "3GPP Release 18 Stage 2 -SA2," 2023.
- [5] 3GPP-RAN, "3GPP Release 18 Stage 2 - RAN," 2023.
- [6] A. Hajrić and et al., "Methods, methodologies, and tools for threat modeling with case study.," *Telfor Journal*, 2020.
- [7] ERICSSON, "3GPP Rel-18 security - the overview," 18 4 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ericsson.com/en/blog/2024/4/3gpp-release-18-security-overview>.
- [8] ETSI, "Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) ETSI," 23 July 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/nfv>.
- [9] P. Porambage and et al., "6G Security Challenges and Potential Solutions," *2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit*, 2021.
- [10] OASIS, "CACAO Security Playbooks Version 2.0," 27 Nov 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.oasis-open.org/cacao/security-playbooks/v2.0/security-playbooks-v2.0.html>.
- [11] A. Darabseh and et al., "SD Security: A Software Defined Security Experimental Framework," 2015.
- [12] M. Pattaranantakul and et al., "SecMANO: Towards Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) Based Security MANagement and Orchestration," 2016.
- [13] H2020-SU-DS-2019, "Palantir Project Description," 1 September 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.palantir-project.eu/>.
- [14] L. L. T. (Chair), *IEEE Recommended Practice for Software Requirements Specifications*, 1998.
- [15] ENISA, "Enisa Threat Landscape," 2023.
- [16] ENISA, "ENISA Threat Landscape for 5G Networks Report," 2020.

**Intelligent Trust and Security Orchestration for 6G Distributed
Cloud Environments**

Co-funded by
the European Union

